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**THE ASEAN WORK PLAN ON EDUCATION (ASED) IN THE TEACHER
EDUCATION PROGRAM OF SELECTED HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS
(HEIs) IN CAMARINES SUR**

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03 November 2023

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Acceptance Page

This thesis titled, "The ASEAN Work Plan on Education (ASED) in the Teacher Education Program of Selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) In Camarines Sur" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, Master of ASEAN Studies.

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Biographical Sketch

The researcher is an educator and agriculture enthusiast. She earned the degree- Doctor of Philosophy in Development Education on April 2017 with academic distinction at Central Bicol State University of Agriculture (CBSUA) – Pili campus and Master of Science in Agricultural Education in 2013 in the same institution.

She was awarded as “Most Outstanding Teacher in DepEd Pili district” and “Most Outstanding Educator” of the Local Government Unit of Pili in 2017. She had been dedicated and committed to instructional service at Del Rosario Elementary School, Pili, Camarines Sur for eight years. On November 2017, she has been part of the tertiary level pool of educators of the College of Education in CBSUA-Calabanga. She participated in various trainings/ seminars in international and national arena and conducted researches in line with student programs, welfare and services, teachers’ development, and instructional materials development which are presented in various research fora.

She is the author of “*Madya na! Mag-adal Kita kan Mother Tongue*” and “*Mathematics: Kontekstuwalisado asin Dyender-Nyutral na Materyal sa Pag-adal para sa mga Kaakian*”. These are contextualized learning materials for Kindergarten and elementary learners with integration of Agriculture, and gender-neutral concepts in the lesson and activities which were written in 4 different languages, namely: Bikol Central, Rinconada-Nabua, English, and Filipino. She also wrote, “Healthy Life Through Healthy Food: A Recipe Book for EPP Grade VI (Book 1-11)” and “Medicine Garden: A Reading Material in EPP for Grade VI”.

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Her endless gratitude and thanksgiving to them.

Dedication

This piece of work is lovingly dedicated to:

Tatay (+), Mama (+), and siblings, niece and nephews

Roger, Jr., Freya, Louis

&

Students, Instructors, & Parents of Higher Education Institutions

Jen C. Aguelo

Abstract

ASEAN awareness The ASEAN Work Plan on Education (ASED) focuses on eight areas including ASEAN awareness through capacity building for teachers and the education community.

This study assessed the implementation of action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in Teacher Education Program of selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Camarines Sur. It aimed to: 1) identify the action lines implemented in Priority Area 1.3, 2) analyze the extent of implementation of the action lines, and 3) examine the challenges encountered by the selected HEIs in the implementation of the action lines. Survey questionnaire was administered to the 359 BSEd and BEEd 4th year students and 93 faculty members /administrators; documentary analysis and Key Informant Interview (KII) with interview guide were done to gather data and analyzed using frequency count, weighted mean, ranking, and 4-point Likert scale.

Results revealed that the three HEIs have diverse action lines relative to ASED such as webinar/ seminar/ training/ lecture activities in collaboration with ASEAN Member States. Action lines are Highly Implemented such as the conduct of conferences/ seminars/ fora on ASEAN. Family financial constraints were the main challenge encountered in the implementation of the action lines.

It is recommended to to initiate and continuously conduct ASED-related activities that will promote the ASEAN awareness in the educational community such as but not limited to quiz bees, essay writing contest, research projects, documentary analysis, and the use of relevant and up-to-date instructional materials, attendance of the faculty in trainings/ seminars in designing an ASEAN-aware curriculum. Further, to establish, coordinate, and manage external linkages and partnerships locally and internationally toward the attainment of ASED targets.

Keywords: ASEAN Work Plan in Education (ASED), Action lines, Teacher Education Program

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Teacher Education Program (TEP) throughout the Philippines serves as one of the many courses offered through different Higher Education Institutions around the country. The curricula for the Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education programs are established by the Commission of Higher Education. The aforementioned subjects encompass general education, education-related subjects, specialized subjects, and practical teaching as outlined in CHED Memorandum Order No. 74 and 75, series of 2017, which are commonly referred to as the Policies, Standards, and Guidelines to earn Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) as well Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd), respectively.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has also issued CMO No. 55 s. 2016, which is commonly referred to as the Policy Framework alongside Strategies on the Internationalization of Philippine Higher Education. This policy was developed in recognition of the historical impetus behind internationalization efforts in higher education, which have traditionally been motivated by academic, social, cultural, and political considerations. The nation is additionally dedicated to promoting the movement of individuals within the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) through the exchange of higher education opportunities among member countries, as outlined in the Master Plan for ASEAN Connectivity 2025.

These objectives align with the stated purpose of the 9th ASEAN Education Ministers Meeting, which took place on May 25, 2016 in Selangor, Malaysia. The 9th

ASEAN Senior Officials Meeting on Education (ASED) acknowledges the inclusion of children and young individuals as a united group of stakeholders and emphasizes their significance in fostering collaboration within the education sector in ASEAN and across its Member States. Recognizing the imperative to enhance the extent of educational collaboration among the member states of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) in order to foster a more synchronized, integrated, and consistent ASEAN stance and its impact on global educational matters, the ministers have endorsed the ASEAN Work Plan on Education 2016-2020. This plan will serve as a guiding framework for educational cooperation over the next five years, and will consolidate all joint endeavors in education with ASEAN Dialogue Partners, international organizations, and other entities that provide support to ASEAN. The Ministers have also endorsed the Framework and Action Plan to support the Kuala Lumpur Declaration on Higher Education, which has been integrated into the ASEAN Work Plan on Education for the period of 2016-2020.

The ASEAN Work Plan on Education centers its attention on eight key domains. These encompass the enhancement of ASEAN awareness by reinforcing knowledge of Southeast Asian history and indigenous wisdom, the improvement of both quality and accessibility of basic education for all individuals, with a particular emphasis on marginalized groups. Additionally, the plan addresses the integration of information and communications technology into educational practices, the advancement of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) as well as lifelong learning opportunities. Furthermore, it underscores the significance of education for sustainable development, the development of higher education and the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms. The plan also highlights the

importance of fostering partnerships between universities and industries, and the necessity of capacity building for teachers and the broader education community.

Given the aforementioned factors, the researcher chose to evaluate the various courses of action within Priority Area 1.3 of the ASEAN on Education Work Plan (ASED), specifically focusing on the Advancing ASEAN Studies Programmes and courses at the higher education level. This evaluation will be conducted through online platforms and cross-border mobility within the Teacher Education Program at selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Camarines Sur.

Statement of the Problem

Generally, the study assessed the implementation of action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for the ASEAN Work Plan on Education (ASED) in Teacher Education Program (TEP) of the selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Camarines Sur. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the action lines implemented in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP of the selected HEIs?
2. What is the extent of implementation of the action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP of the selected HEIs? And
3. What are the challenges faced by the chosen Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in incorporating the action lines of Priority Area 1.3 for Accelerating Sustainable Economic Development (ASED) into their Teaching Enhancement Plans (TEP)?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to assess the implementation of action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for the ASEAN Work Plan on Education (ASED) in Teacher Education Program of the selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Camarines Sur. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. identify the action lines implemented in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP of the selected HEIs;
2. analyze the extent of implementation of the action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP of the selected HEIs; and
3. examine the challenges encountered by the selected HEIs in the implementation of the action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED into their TEP.

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on assessing the implementation of action lines in Priority Area 1.3 of the ASEAN Work Plan on Education from 2016-2020 of the Teacher Education Program offered by the selected public HEIs in Camarines Sur. Other program offerings of the selected HEIs are not included as part of the study. The assessment also includes the profile of the respondents and challenges encountered in the implementation of the action lines. It involved the randomly selected fourth year students taking BEED and BSED degree programs, as well as teachers handling the major and elective courses, and the school administrators.

Significance of the Study

The researcher perceived this study to be beneficial in assessing the action lines being implemented by the respondent HEIs in terms of their efforts in integrating ASEAN concepts in their Teacher Education Program. It served as a starter for studies of the same theme. Specifically, this study is deemed significant to the following:

Students. One of the important aspects that the students can benefit from is the awareness and experience of engaging themselves to varied programs and projects initiated for ASED by their institution as it commits in the aspiration of regional organization. Prospective teachers who are aware and knowledgeable of ASED will eventually transmit the same appreciation, knowledge, and awareness to their prospective students.

Teachers. The acquisition of knowledge is crucial for individuals, as it enables them to gain a deeper understanding of various subjects. Consequently, being aware of the findings of this research would provide individuals with additional opportunities to acquire the essential information pertaining to the roles and objectives of the ASEAN organization in the field of education. This, in turn, could enhance their level of dedication and effectiveness in implementing the ASEAN Work Plan on Education.

Parents. This would also serve as an instrument for the parents to realize their importance and role in their child/children's education, as well as their responsibilities as one of the stakeholders of the institution. Their involvement is one of the primary factors in the achievement of their children and of the school towards the attainment of ASED.

School administrators. Administrators would recommend to the curriculum planners, teachers, and other personalities involved to craft policies to uplift the ASED such as promoting the teachers and students exchange programs, strengthening the partnership between foreign and local education institutions, as well as enhancing the faculty knowledge in terms of ASEAN organization.

Teacher Education. The results of this research could be a basis for the department to plan and develop curriculum which integrates ASEAN concepts in the curriculum both in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities.

Commission on Higher Education. The agency would gain knowledge and significant information in terms of the selected HEIs program compliance related to ASED. In return, they could assess and propose recommendations for its improvement and sustainability.

Researchers. This study could serve as basis for another study. They can get ideas to conceptualize further studies pertaining to ASED.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents the readings of literature gathered from books, published and unpublished theses, and other sources of information which will provide insights necessary in the realization of this study. It also includes the illustrations of theoretical and conceptual frameworks in relation to the present study.

ASEAN on Education and the Role of Education

In their study, Katigbak and Amante (2019) underscore the pivotal role of higher education in advancing the objectives of ASEAN integration. They emphasize that higher education is poised to significantly contribute to bolstering regional political, economic, and socio-cultural development while bridging the development gap among member nations. The multifaceted contributions of higher education to these aspirations encompass the enhancement of economic competitiveness, As stated by the ASEAN Secretariat (2008b, 2009a), the development of human capital and the uniformity of the systems for higher education are priorities. These duties are clearly reflected in the European Union's approach, particularly through initiatives like as the Europe 2020 strategy, which lays a heavy emphasis on knowledge-based economic growth and job creation. Furthermore, the EU promotes supportive initiatives such as the Bologna Process and the Lisbon Strategy, which align with higher education objectives in the larger context of the integration of regions.

The ASEAN Secretariat, as highlighted in the ASEAN State of Education Report, emphasizes the pivotal role of education within the ASEAN Socio Cultural

Community (ASCC). This community has been charged with ensuring that the ASEAN workforce is appropriately prepared for and benefits from the integration of the economy. This is accomplished through increased investment in various aspects of education, training, science and technology development, job creation, and social protection, as outlined in the Declaration of ASEAN Concord II. As a result, the ASCC places a major priority on education, recognizing that human resource development as well as empowerment are critical strategies for increasing employment opportunities, reducing poverty and socioeconomic disparities, and promoting inequity.

True to its mission, the ASCC has achieved notable success in several key education-related areas, including improvements in enrollment rates, literacy rates among adults and youth, reductions in school drop-out rates, and advancements in gender parity at both elementary and secondary education levels. These enhancements within the educational systems of ASEAN member states have spurred the ASCC to further advocate for robust educational cooperation among member countries. This cooperative approach is designed to bridge development gaps, prepare the youth for leadership roles in the region, and enhance the competitiveness of ASEAN citizens on the global stage, as highlighted in the research by Agustin and Montebo (2018).

Education plays several crucial roles in supporting the achievement of ASEAN goals within the Socio-cultural sphere. These roles encompass a range of key objectives, including: a) The development of standardized content related to ASEAN, to be integrated into school and university curricula. b) Promoting ASEAN languages and cultures as integral components of school curricula. c) The facilitation of cross-border exchanges among youth and students to enhance cultural understanding and

cooperation. d) Advocating for educational accessibility, promoting lifelong learning, and aligning with the "Education for All" program. e) Establishing the ASEAN Educational Research Convention to promote educational research and development (ASEAN Secretariat, 2009).

Furthermore, the role of higher education within the educational framework supports the goals of ASEAN in specific ways. Each member countries must adjust its legislation in order to achieve the goal of regional integration, which is to eradicate trade obstacles and increase the volume of trade in higher education services. These changes make it easier for higher education service providers from other member countries to compete equally in home markets (Kuroda, Yuki, and Kyuwon 2010; World Trade Organization 2001).

Aligned with the 1987 Philippine Constitution and Republic Act No. 7722 provisions, commonly referred to as the "Higher Education Act of 1994," the ASEAN Integration initiative is set to usher in a range of transformative changes. These changes include: 1) Facilitating increased mobility of human resources, which is expected to impact the educational landscape substantially; 2) Prompting a heightened emphasis on competitiveness and the quality of graduates and educational programs to meet the demands of this integrated regional environment; and 3) Fostering enhanced regional collaboration in the realms of education and research, further bolstering the cooperative efforts within the ASEAN community (Nicolas, 2014).

ASEAN Post-2015 Vision on Education

The vision for education in the ASEAN region beyond 2015 was formally outlined and adopted during the 8th ASEAN Ministers Meeting on Education (ASEM8),

which took place on September 11, 2014, in Vientiane, Lao PDR. This vision encompasses several vital principles and objectives. First and foremost, the ASEAN education sector is committed to promoting a community that places people at its core, fostering a deep sense of awareness and unity within the ASEAN community. Secondly, the sector remains resolute in its dedication to sustainable development throughout the region, recognizing education's crucial role in achieving this goal. Finally, ensuring access to quality inclusive education and the development of lifelong learning is a fundamental priority of this vision. This will be accomplished through the implementation of rigorous capacity-building initiatives as well as the provision of structural guidelines to govern the development of education in the ASEAN community.

Program/Project/Activities Toward ASEAN on Education

Several scholars have emphasized the importance of higher education in various initiatives and activities, including Butter (2006), Knight (2012), and Terada (2003). These programs address issues like as workforce mobility, regional identity, and the liberalization of trade in higher educational services. Nevertheless, as the OECD stated in 2009, the efficient execution of these operations has been hampered by the diversity of academic degrees, certifications, as well as quality assurance systems among member nations.

In response to these challenges, the process of regional integration incorporates a policy of harmonizing higher education within the integration framework. Higher education harmonization is a deliberate process aimed at acknowledging the diversity in higher education, fostering connections between

different higher education systems, and promoting the adoption of common guidelines and practices to enhance cooperation in this crucial realm.

Student Mobility

Student mobility is a concept that encompasses the movement of students from their home countries to foreign destinations for the primary purpose of pursuing higher education, Scholars such as Junor and Usher (2008), the OECD (2009), and UNESCO (2009) all agree on this point. Vertical mobility and horizontal mobility are the two main types of student mobility.

Vertical mobility refers to students completing their whole degree program in a foreign country, whereas horizontal mobility refers to shorter-term study experiences abroad, frequently in the form of student exchanges. In cases of horizontal mobility, students typically complete specific modules or courses but do not pursue an entire degree program. These distinctions in student mobility are further elucidated by the research of Solimano (2008) and Teichler (2003, 2011). The "Learning: Getting to Know ASEAN Better" website, managed by the ASEAN Secretariat, serves as a platform to showcase ASEAN-related courses and research centers, a point highlighted by Azmawati and Quayle in their work from 2017. Furthermore, the program focused on student and teacher mobility is critical in assessing the standardization of higher education systems and the advancement of regional economic integration.

The degree of student and teacher mobility is an important indicator of several factors, including the reciprocal recognition of credits and degrees, as well as the general volume of labor mobility. Furthermore, this mobility has broader implications, such as enhancing the employability of graduates, facilitating the transfer of technology and intellectual assets, and fostering cultural awareness, all of which

contribute to the advancement of regional integration, encompassing both economic and political dimensions, as observed in the research by Rexeisen et al. in 2008.

Chao's study from 2020 delves into the context of student mobility within ASEAN, revealing a significant contrast between intra-ASEAN student mobility and the outward flow of students from ASEAN countries. This discovery is consistent with the research conducted by Chan in 2012, which emphasizes the phenomenon of a significant number of students migrating from different Asian countries to Western nations. As a result, there is a discernible pattern of regionalization or horizontal movement of students within the Asian region that is becoming increasingly apparent. The increased competition among Asian nations for students from the same demographic introduces a level of intricacy to the current scenario. Consequently, this phenomenon poses a significant threat to the prominent Western universities' involvement in the attraction of international students to Asia via transnational higher education endeavors. The escalating competition between local and international higher education institutions presents novel governance concerns for host countries in the Asian region. In order to tackle these concerns, Chao (2020) proposes the establishment of an extensive intra-ASEAN mobility program, which takes inspiration from current intra-ASEAN mobility initiatives and is informed by advancements in European ERASMUS mobility programs.

This advice is based on a comparative analysis of student mobility programs, specifically focusing on three initiatives: the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization-Regional Institution of Higher Education and Development, University Mobility in Asia and the Pacific (UMAP), and Campus Asia. The findings of the study indicate that the ASEAN International Mobility for Students (AIMS), Collective Action for Mobility Program of University Students in Asia (CAMPUS Asia), and UMAP

student mobility schemes all aim to promote regionalization in higher education. Nevertheless, these entities implement unique regulatory frameworks and employ diverse functional, organizational, and political approach models. The AIMS and CAMPUS Asia networks, which are governed by respective governments, utilize a comprehensive approach that encompasses functional, organizational, and political strategies. In contrast, UMAP provides regional mobility initiatives that are driven by universities and employ a hybridized approach. However, it is important to note that these three projects face comparable obstacles on both regional and national scales. These issues include the existence of diverse national legislation, the need for effective coordination among participating entities, and the successful implementation of credit transfer mechanisms. As a result, the scope of these three student mobility initiatives is now constrained, so constraining their influence on the process of higher education regionalization in Asia. According to Hou et al. (2017), it is considered crucial to improve the decision-making process and provide greater financial assistance to institutions and students in order to develop a sustainable and efficient network.

In the study conducted by Soejatminah (2018), the author delves into the subject of internationalization in higher education and its impact on fostering regional collaborations and student mobility. While existing research has extensively examined patterns of student mobility, there is a dearth of studies focusing on the transformative potential of regional mobility networks. The ASEAN University Network (AUN) serves as the primary regional network of universities in Southeast Asia, with a dedicated commitment to promoting student mobility within the region. The study highlights that AUN has successfully established regional quality assurance and credit transfer systems to facilitate the movement of students across

member universities. Notably, the implementation of the Indonesian qualification framework has further strengthened AUN's operationalization of the credit transfer system within its member institutions.

Faculty Mobility

Faculty mobility refers to the phenomenon in which educators choose to relocate from their countries of origin to different nations in order to participate in teaching, training, and research endeavors. This concept has been extensively studied and discussed in the literature, as evidenced by the works of OECD (2009) and van de Bunt-Kokhuis (2000). The exchange of students and faculty members across national borders is widely recognized as a significant mechanism for facilitating the transmission of knowledge and skills between countries. This practice plays a crucial role in promoting academic and research collaboration, while also helping to reduce economic development gaps within the region. This viewpoint is supported by the scholarly works of Knight (2012), Neubauer (2012), and the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2009).

The study undertaken by Abulon et al. (2017) involved Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) as respondents who provided recommendations for a series of mobility interventions. These interventions were designed to develop an academic mobility framework among Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) in the ASEAN region. The recommendations encompass several key areas: firstly, promoting collaboration among ASEAN TEIs to enhance the visibility of their teacher education programs; secondly, improving English language proficiency; thirdly, augmenting financial assistance for both student and faculty mobility; and finally, advancing curriculum development to achieve harmonization. The mobility framework that has been put up encompasses three fundamental elements: the underlying objective of

mobility within ASEAN TEIs, the several domains of mobility, and the mechanisms that enable and support it. The envisioned objective of teacher mobility within the ASEAN setting is to serve as a catalyst for the development of the ASEAN socio-cultural community. The objective of this initiative is to facilitate mobility programs among higher education institutions in the ASEAN region, which will include many aspects such as academic, research, extension, and cultural components. The successful implementation of these programs requires the incorporation of facilitating mechanisms, such as academic synchronization, curriculum comparisons, cross-crediting systems, considerations with regard to the medium of instruction as well as the delivery format, and essential funding support coming from regional institutions. The provided mobility framework functions as a guiding plan for ASEAN TEIs, namely within the ASEAN Teacher Education Network (ASTEN), as they strive to establish mobility programs in the realm of teacher education.

Graduate Employability

Graduate employability is widely recognized as a crucial factor in the process of advancing regional economic development and integration, while concurrently elevating the standards of education, its efficiency, and accountability. As a result, considering the expected favorable outcomes of enhancing graduate employability, numerous regional institutions have instituted initiatives aimed at facilitating the movement of students and faculty members. Prominent instances of such endeavors encompass the ASEAN International Mobility for Students (AIMS) initiative situated within the ASEAN framework, the Erasmus Programs established within the European Union (EU), as well as the University Mobility in Asia and the Pacific (UMAP) program working under the auspices of the APEC framework. The aforementioned initiatives are influenced by the knowledge and perspectives offered

by esteemed researchers and scholars including Hawkins (2012), Neubauer (2012), OECD (2009), Solimano (2008), and Teichler (2011). These experts have emphasized the importance of these mobility programs in cultivating the employability of graduates and promoting regional development and integration.

Mutual Credit and Degree Recognition

The process of harmonization gives rise to the essential components of mutual recognition and degree recognition. This comprehensive acknowledgment encompasses credentials at various educational levels, including credits obtained from international educational institutions and the granting of professional and academic designations in foreign nations, as discussed in the literature by Butter (2006), Hawkins (2012), and Teichler (2011). The overarching objective is to improve the standardization and clarity of credits, degrees, and qualifications across a wide range of educational institutions. Through the implementation of recognition, it is ensured that students have attained recognized accomplishments prior to pursuing advanced studies, and graduates are treated fairly and impartially, irrespective of their educational histories. Therefore, it is expected that this method will result in an increase in both student and workforce mobility.

The concept of mutual recognition and degree recognition involves the thorough analysis, comparison, and establishment of standardized frameworks for qualifications along with quality assurance systems in many nations. This notion is emphasized by Teichler (2011). By examining the outcomes of ASEAN, the African Union (AU), and the European Union (EU), it becomes evident that these frameworks are based on the length of study and the anticipated achievements of students. The duration of study refers to the temporal extent of academic pursuits and the allocation of credit hours within the tripartite framework of bachelor's,

master's, and doctorate degrees. The implementation of regulated study durations has led to the initiation of revisions in higher education institutions throughout Europe. Before the introduction of the Bologna Process, several European nations, including Germany, France, and the Netherlands, did not conform to the three-cycle degree or credit-hour framework. The presence of differing study durations presents issues not only within Europe, but also within the ASEAN and AU regions. In both instances, it is observed that member nations have not consistently embraced a credit-hour system, and their degree frameworks are founded on distinct models, leading to varied periods of study, notably at the undergraduate level.

To resolve these inequalities and achieve effective harmonization, regional organizations and their member countries must engage in talks, mutual understanding, and the inclusion of student results in credentials and quality certification systems.

Lifelong Learning

The primary focus of lifelong learning revolves around the enhancement of the labor force and the promotion of partnership between higher education institutions and the business sectors. The primary objective of this method is to substantially augment the employability of those who have completed their education. Within the current body of literature, the concept of employability is frequently characterized as the ability to successfully obtain employment in any given occupation. Nevertheless, this research adopts a more nuanced approach by delineating employability as the capacity to attain employment that correspond to the credentials and educational attainment of individuals. The use of the employability concept within the framework of regional economic integration refers to the active search of employment prospects, encompassing both domestic and international contexts. This

understanding aligns with the definition put forth by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 2009.

To bolster the employability of graduates, higher education institutions and the business sectors must collaborate closely. This collaboration ensures that degree and training programs are tailored to equip graduates and the workforce with the essential competencies to thrive in the ever-evolving job market.

Human Capital Development

The policies implemented by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) aim to promote the development of human capital by focusing on improving the employability of graduates. These policies are not limited to the national labor market but also extend to the larger regional labor markets. The aforementioned regulations exemplify the response of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to the dynamic environment in which companies are assuming a progressively powerful position in creating the realm of higher education. Eckel and King (2004) have noticed that individuals are perceived as both advocates and consumers of higher education offerings. The forthcoming integration of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) is expected to facilitate an increased volume of trade and enhanced mobility of the workforce across national boundaries. There is a projected substantial expansion in labor markets, with a change from predominantly national to increasingly regional scopes. In the given context, individuals who have completed their education and individuals seeking employment must demonstrate not just exceptional proficiency in their respective professional skills, but also gain supplementary proficiencies such as foreign language aptitude and the capacity to effectively participate in cross-cultural communication.

In addition, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has implemented the Faculty Development Project, which is based on the fundamental belief that the caliber of faculty members significantly influences the standard of both primary and vocational education. By enhancing the caliber of high school educators, this initiative is poised to improve the standard of secondary education, thereby guaranteeing that students are adequately equipped for success in higher education. The primary objective of the faculty development initiative revolves around enhancing the proficiency of educators, with a specific emphasis on the disciplines of English language, basic sciences, and mathematics.

ASEAN Awareness through education and other agencies

Education and other governmental institutions in the Philippines have actively engaged in promoting and disseminating information of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) among their students, faculty, and the general public. In the year 2018, a significant endeavor took place involving the implementation of various endeavors aimed at enhancing the understanding and knowledge of ASEAN among the student body of First Asia Institute of Technology and Humanities (FAITH) Colleges, as well as the local inhabitants of Tanauan, Batangas. This initiative was made possible through a collaborative effort between the Department of Foreign Affairs (DFA) and FAITH Colleges. The presentation on ASEAN centered on the advantages of the organization for young individuals and its role in fostering the development of the ASEAN Community. Participants in the talk included kids from Grades 11-12 and college students who were specifically chosen. The representative from the Department of Foreign Affairs (DFA) elaborated on the current state of ASEAN collaboration in the field of education, specifically highlighting the ASEAN Mutual Recognition Arrangements. This initiative seeks to enhance the

ease of movement for professionals and skilled workers within the ASEAN region by promoting the exchange of information and the adoption of standardized qualifications and best practices. The ASEAN Qualifications Reference Framework facilitates the evaluation and comparison of educational qualifications among ASEAN Member States, with the aim of promoting mobility for students and workers. Additionally, the ASEAN University Network was deliberated upon, which permits students from accredited universities to enroll in courses offered by other institutions within the network.

Robles and Parlelo (2017) explicate that it is imperative for every member country of the global village to align its social dimension of progress and development with the standards of global and regional convergence. In context, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) has entered into another milestone consequent to the adoption of blueprints for an integrated local community. This involves a deeper coordination between ASEAN's ten (10) members for a more enhanced political, economic, and security, cultural and social integration (Hayton and Thuzar, 2016). A region-wide survey of (Thompson and Thianthai, 2008) articulated the high level of awareness on ASEAN Integration among undergraduate university students in Southeast Asian nations. Additionally, empirical evidence has demonstrated that students exhibit favorable sentiments towards regional economic cooperation and express agreement when asked about their identification as members of such cooperative initiatives. In contrast to the aforementioned hopeful perspective, it is evident that the key drivers of the integration of ASEAN face a prevailing atmosphere characterized by worry and pressure. This can be attributed to the notable prevalence of apathy among inhabitants of the ASEAN region. In 2013, the ASEAN Secretariat revealed that three out of four ASEAN citizens (76 percent)

lack a basic understanding of what ASEAN is and what it strives to do. The report concluded that the overall level of agreement for both businesses and the general public is still low because of a prevailing lack of interest along with an ineffective use of communication channels (Domingo, 2013).

Domingo (2012) as cited by Sunga argued the slower growth in the economic standing of ASEAN as tighter financial concerns were encountered due to the destabilization of financial markets in the region. She also added that according to the study released by the ASEAN Secretariat, it was found out that three out of four people “lack a basic understanding” of what the organization and its objectives is all about. Also, four out of five are “familiar with” the ASEAN. During the conduct of the report in 2012, the results of the study “significantly surpassed the expected public awareness,” according to the ASEAN Secretariat. Additionally, the study revealed that 55% of participants in the business sector possess a "fundamental comprehension" of ASEAN, while 30% lack any "elementary understanding" of this particular region. It further affirmed that “regardless of low level of awareness, the survey showed that the overall perception and attitude towards the ASEAN community is positive (Sunga as cited by Domingo, 2012).

The awareness on ASEAN is low among its own citizens (Jayaraman, 2017). She emphasized that this is one way to make ways to intensify the needs to gauge awareness among citizens of ASEAN Member States (AMS) on the significance of creating an ASEAN-centric community. The findings of Thompson and Thianthai's (2007) study indicate that the levels of awareness and knowledge regarding ASEAN were highest in Vietnam, Laos, Brunei, and Indonesia, while they were comparatively lower in Singapore and the Philippines. It was observed that in 2007, the level of

awareness and understanding regarding ASEAN integration in the Philippines was comparatively lower than that of other member countries within the ASEAN region.

Efforts to enhance awareness of ASEAN were initiated by a range of entities, encompassing governmental bodies, commercial enterprises, media outlets, and academic institutions. An agreement was reached between Rappler, a well-known social news network, and the Asian Institute of Management (AIM) to collaborate on producing a series of narratives that elucidate the importance and consequences of ASEAN integration for the general public (Ranada, 2015). Also, the ASEAN Business Advisory Council strengthens the thrust toward ASEAN by organizing a recognition program for Philippine companies, which has contributed to the growth and advancement of the ASEAN economy (Miraflor, 2014). The significance of these awareness programs is underscored by Min's (2015) observation that a key obstacle in the process of ASEAN Integration is the need to enhance the understanding and recognition of the advantages associated with the regional economic community among the populace.

ASEAN as a Regional Organization

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) is a regional alliance consisting of 10 member states, including Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. The major objective of the organization is to promote economic and security collaboration among its member states. The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) has been instrumental in promoting economic integration in the Asian area. It has actively engaged in discussions to build the largest free trade agreement globally and has successfully entered into six free trade agreements with adjacent

economies. The organization functions under the governance of a rotating presidency, wherein member nations undergo an annual shift of leadership. The presence of a secretariat situated in Jakarta; Indonesia serves as more evidence to corroborate this claim. In the realm of decision-making, it is customary for key determinations to be reached by a process of consultations and consensus. These deliberations are underpinned by the values of noninterference in internal affairs and the pursuit of peaceful resolutions to conflicts.

The Member States of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) assembled with the collective objective of establishing the ASEAN Community by the year 2015 and formulating the ASEAN Community Vision 2025. The aforementioned aims align with ASEAN's vision of establishing a cohesive, harmonious, and secure community, as stated on the official ASEAN website. According to Club (2016), the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), Department of Education (DepEd), along with Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) play crucial roles as constituent elements within the ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community (ASCC), which is one of the three pillars of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). This alignment is in harmony with the views expressed on the asean.org website, which underscores the significance of education in the ASCC and acknowledges its pivotal role in the construction of the ASEAN Community. Education is seen as a vehicle for raising awareness about ASEAN, fostering a collective sense of belonging, and nurturing an understanding of the richness of ASEAN's history, languages, culture, and shared values. The deepening and broadening of ASEAN in the realm of education represent a collaborative endeavor among the member states. As such, it becomes essential to assess the programs

and initiatives undertaken by Higher Education Institutions as they work toward realizing the goals of the ASEAN Community.

People's Attitudes toward ASEAN within and beyond the region

The research conducted by Siraprapasiri with na Thalang in 2016 provided significant findings. The study confirmed that maintaining favorable sentiments towards the ASEAN region plays a crucial role in fostering optimistic hopes for ASEAN. Furthermore, the research findings unveiled a significant revelation: knowledge about ASEAN, when considered in isolation, is insufficient to comprehensively account for students' attitudes toward ASEAN, and it does not consistently lead to positive attitudes. The implications of these findings, along with those derived from Focus Group Discussions (FGD), point to the necessity of a high level of knowledge and understanding regarding fellow ASEAN member countries and their respective populations. This understanding can be acquired through formal education, informal learning, or social interaction. Such knowledge is a crucial foundation for students to cultivate positive attitudes and become aspiring members of the ASEAN Community.

In a study by Benny and Abdullah in 2011, The study observed that Indonesian participants, although possessing a very restricted understanding of the proposed establishment of the ASEAN Community, exhibited substantial endorsement for the concept. Furthermore, the individuals showcased support for the creation of the regional community encompassing its three fundamental foundations: the Security Community, Economic Community, and Socio-Cultural Community. Furthermore, the Indonesian participants expressed their perception that the establishment of the community will generate advantages not just for their country but also for society and the whole economy.

The viewpoints on ASEAN across a sample of around 2,000 students from important colleges within ASEAN member nations demonstrate significant parallels in their attitudes. The poll results indicated a growing sense of ownership and active involvement with the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), however there were discernible differences in levels of knowledge and perspectives toward the organization. A agreement was reached by the students on the vital importance of economic cooperation and the necessity to address poverty and developmental requirements. Furthermore, the participants collectively conveyed a mutual enthusiasm to enhance their comprehension of the area, as articulated by Thompson and Thianthai in their 2008 study.

The study conducted by Robles and Parlelo in 2017 revealed that Pre-Service Teachers in the SOCKSARGEN region exhibited favorable reactions towards ASEAN integration. Nevertheless, this viewpoint contradicts the conclusions drawn by Benny et al. in their study conducted in 2015. Numerous regional observers exhibited a sense of skepticism about the establishment of the ASEAN Community (AC) in their research, as they perceived it as a notion that might appear excessively idealistic given the prevailing regional dynamics. According to Kavi Chongkittarn, a Senior Fellow at the Institute of Strategic and International Studies, Chulalongkorn University, it is not anticipated that the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) will progress towards a trajectory similar to that of the European Union (EU). However, similar to the European Union, it is important to acknowledge that the establishment of an Asian Community will require more than just rhetoric and diplomatic niceties. Ikrar Nusa Bakti, the former chairman of the Department of Political Studies at the Indonesian Institute of Science, expressed comparable doubts, asserting that ASEAN has historically been regarded as an exclusive entity,

subject to the influence of bureaucrats and politicians. The inclusion of the general public within ASEAN is vital in order to ensure the organization's relevance to its member states as well as to external states beyond the region. The active participation of the general populace of ASEAN member states in the establishment of the ASEAN Community has been limited.

In addition, with regards to the integration of ASEAN, it is worth noting that there is a significant dearth of public opinion indicators inside the area, and the availability of studies examining public opinion is limited. The literature pertaining to the notion and ideals of an ASEAN Community predominantly draws upon the scholarly perspectives of numerous academics. There has been a scarcity of research conducted on the subject of popular perceptions towards the ASEAN Community. Benny et al. (2015) have observed a notable gap in the existing research on ASEAN regionalism, namely on the lack of public perspectives and responses towards the ASEAN Community concept.

The Goal of ASEAN Community

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) serves as a platform for the nations in Southeast Asia to come together with the shared objective of fostering amicable relations and collaboration. Their aim is to ensure the well-being and prosperity of their citizens and future generations via joint endeavors and acts of selflessness. The aforementioned vision serves as the foundation for the objectives of the ASEAN Community as well as ASEAN Integration.

The primary objective involves the formation of an ASEAN Community that prioritizes the well-being of its citizens, placing emphasis on dynamism and societal accountability. This involves fostering constructive engagement with various sectors,

including academia, parliamentarians, women, youth, and civil society groups, as outlined during the 25th ASEAN Summit in 2014.

The second objective seeks to elevate ASEAN's effectiveness in fulfilling the aspirations of its people, encompassing good governance, transparency, improved living standards, sustainable development with a focus on climate change and environmental concerns, greater empowerment of women, and enhanced opportunities for all in the post-2015 era. These aspirations were articulated during the 26th ASEAN Summit in 2015.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter provides an overview of the research designs employed, the study's region and respondents, the research instrument utilized, the data gathering technique, the data analysis approach, and the ethical issues taken into account in order to obtain the study's findings and outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded in the theoretical framework of Neo-functionalism. Neo-functionalism, as conceptualized by Ernst Haas during the mid-1950s, aims to facilitate enhanced integration across nations while avoiding excessive or rapid integration pressures. Neo-functionalism is commonly linked to the objectives of politics and economics, as well as the techniques of integration (Dunn, 2012). Regional integration is defined by the deepening of connections between autonomous and sovereign governments, leading to collaborative efforts based on consistent and predictable patterns of conduct.

This theory provides a description and explanation of the phenomenon of regional integration. According to the findings of Katigbak and Amante (2019), the theory posits a significant role for non-state actors, including colleges and universities, in shaping the trajectory of integration efforts. These actors possess the potential to apply pressure on the national government, hence encouraging increased participation in regional integration arrangements. The integration of higher education facilitates the participation of member-countries and their inhabitants in the unrestricted movement of capital, labor, services, goods, and

foreign investments. It emphasizes the economic state which can also be linked to socio-cultural communities. Central to the latter is the significance of education, such as Teacher Education Program in promoting peoples' well-being and human dignity through interaction between and among HEIs of the member states of ASEAN specifically members of AUN.

One feature of the integration is to promote mobility of students, develop and implement regional initiatives on education (asean.org) which is likewise the target of ASED specifically in Priority Area 1.3. The ASED Work Plan aims to provide assistance and execute the ASEAN Post-2015 Vision on Education. It seeks to enhance, intensify, and broaden educational collaboration with various partners. Additionally, it strives to broaden the range of educational cooperation in order to develop a more unified, comprehensive, and consistent ASEAN stance on education matters, while also contributing to global education concerns. The achievement of these ASED aims is most likely to be realized through regional integration.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual paradigm of this study illuminated the processes and what to expect to find through in this research. This would shed light on the flow and interpretation of the target outcome which is to generate a recommendation to achieve an advanced ASEAN studies courses in TEP through the assessment of action lines of the ASED in TEP offered by the selected Higher Education Institutions in the Bicol region. Along with the implementation are the possible challenges encountered which are believed to be factors that influence the attainment of advanced ASEAN Studies Courses in TEP.

Figure 2. Conceptual paradigm.

Research Design

The research employed the descriptive methodology. The study utilized a descriptive research approach to document and provide a comprehensive description of the activities and level of implementation of the action lines in Priority Area 1.3 of the ASEAN Work Plan on Education (ASED) inside the Teacher Education Program of the chosen public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Camarines Sur.

Gathered results serve as evidence-based information for developing or crafting recommendations to attain an advanced ASEAN Studies courses for ASED in the TEP of the respondent HEIs.

Locale of the Study

The respondents for this study consisted of three (3) public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) situated in the province of Camarines Sur, which is located in the Bicol region. They were selected based on the criteria that HEIs should have the existing offering of Teacher Education degree programs both in secondary and elementary.

The researcher employed a combination of primary and secondary sources of data. The main sources of data comprised the replies obtained from the questionnaire and the interviews conducted with the participants. The secondary data were composed of the available and relevant documents from the respondents in terms of their programs and activities related to ASED, as well as from published studies, reference books, and reports from ASEAN and its secretariat found from online platforms.

Figure 3. The location of the HEIs in the province of Camarines Sur.

Source: *mapsofworld.com*

Respondents and Sampling Design

The researcher employed a combination of primary and secondary sources of data. The main sources of data comprised the replies obtained from the questionnaire and the interviews conducted with the participants.

Higher Education Institutions. The respondent public HEIs were from Naga City, Goa, Camarines Sur and Pili, Camarines Sur.

Respondents. The user's text is not sufficient to be rewritten in an academic manner. The study's participants consisted of individuals from various educational backgrounds, including students, faculty members, and administrators from a carefully chosen group of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). A random selection of students pursuing a degree in secondary and primary teacher education was conducted using a lottery technique. The registrar provided a roster of enrolled pupils

to aid in the selecting process. The researchers employed purposive sampling in order to select faculty-respondents who were responsible for teaching major and elective courses, as well as school administrators.

The sample size was determined using the Slovin's formula: $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$, where; n = sample size; N = Total Population; and e = margin of error (e) set at 5 percent (5%). Table 1 presented the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1

Distribution of the Respondents of the Study

HEIs	No. of Respondents				TOTAL	
	Students		Faculty/Administrators		N	n
	N	n	N	n		
1	168	135	35	32	203	167
2	100	86	31	28	131	114
3	211	138	36	33	247	171
TOTAL	479	359	102	93	581	452

Legend:

N- Total number of population

n- Sample size

Profile of the Respondents

Respondents' profile examined in the study were the following: A.) For the students, the following were determined; i.) year level and ii.) degree and major taken. B.) For the faculty and administrators, information about the i.) academic qualification, ii.) number of years in the service, iii) course/s taught, iv.) degree program taught and v) position were assessed.

A. Students

Year level. 100 percent of the students enrolled in fourth year level taking BSE and BEED courses in the three public HEIs composed the respondents/ participants of this study.

Degree and major taken. According to the data presented in Table 2, it can be observed that 33 percent of the participants were enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) program, whilst the remaining 67 percent belonged to the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSE) program. In particular, 18 percent was Mathematics major, 8 percent belonged to Filipino major, 13 percent of the respondents was taking the degree in BSE major in Science and 23 percent was major in English, while the remaining 3 and 1 percent of the respondents were major in Social Studies and Values Education, respectively.

B. Faculty/Administrators

Academic qualification. 43 percent of the respondents was doctorate degree holder, 24 percent of the faculty were master degree holder, 14 percent earned units in doctorate degree, while 10 percent have units in master degree and 9 percent was bachelor degree holder.

Number of years in the service. Faculty/administrators in the 3 HEIs belonged to the 16-20 years was composed of 26 percent, 6-10 years in the service were 21 percent, 19 percent of the respondents worked for 11-15 years, 18 percent has rendered services for 21-26 years in their institution, and both 8 percent rendered services for 1-5 and 27 years and above.

Degree program taught. Instruction, as one of the mandates of the three public Higher Education Institutions, required teaching personnel to render instruction services in spite of the designations assigned to them by the university

higher authorities. Thus, based on the survey, teachers and faculty handling administrative positions both taught in the BSE and BEED programs.

Table 2

Distribution of Responses along Degree and Major Taken, Academic Qualifications, and Number of Years in the Service of the Respondents

Degree and major taken						
DEGREE	MAJOR	HEIs			TOTAL	%
		1	2	3		
BSEd	Math	34	23	31	88	18
	Filipino	0	11	29	40	8
	Science	37	2	24	63	13
	English	46	24	40	110	23
	Social Studies	0	15	0	15	3
	Values Education	0	5	0	5	1
	TOTAL		117	80	124	321
BEEd		51	20	87	158	33
	TOTAL (BSEd & BEEd)	168	100	211	479	100
Academic qualifications						
Bachelor degree		2	1	6	9	9
With Units in Master degree		5	5	0	10	10
Master degree		8	5	11	24	24
With units in doctorate degree		7	8	0	15	14
Doctorate degree		13	12	19	44	43
TOTAL		35	31	36	102	100
Number of years in the service						
1-5		1	2	5	8	8
6-10		8	5	8	21	21
11-15		7	8	5	20	19
16-20		8	9	10	27	26
21-26		7	5	6	18	18
27 & above		4	2	2	8	8
TOTAL		35	31	33	102	100

HEI1 offers BSE major in Mathematics, Science, and English. HEI2 has 6 majors in BSE program, namely; Mathematics, Filipino, Science, English, Social Studies, and Values Education while HEI3 offers BSE major in Mathematics, Filipino, Science, and English.

Courses taught. Professional Education courses, Major courses, General Education courses, and Electives are being taught by the respondent faculty/administrators. The curricula for BSEd and BEEd are based on CHED Memorandum Order No. 74 series of 2017, which is titled "Policies, Standards and Guidelines for Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd)," and CHED Memorandum Order No. 75 series of 2017, titled "Policies, Standards and Guidelines for Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)."

Some of the curriculum components under the Professional Education courses include the following: The Teacher and the School Curriculum, The Teaching Profession, Teaching Internship, Assessment in Learning, and Technology for Teaching and Learning.

Major courses are in accordance with the degree program and major being offered by the HEIs. Mathematics, Physics, English, Filipino, Research and BEED major courses such as Science, Filipino, Social Studies, MAPEH, MTB MLE, and Research are among the major courses handled by the faculty/administrators.

Some of the General Education courses are as follows; Readings in the Philippine History; Art Appreciation; Ethics; The Contemporary World; The Life and Works of Rizal; Understanding the Self; and Science, Technology, and Society.

Peace Education, Indigenous Peoples Studies, and Gender Studies are the Elective courses in HEI2; ASEAN Integration, Foreign language, and Agriculture subjects in HEI3, and about the Renewable Energy in HEI1.

Position. Among the positions/ designations of the respondents are the following: Program Chairperson/Director in BEED and BSED, Internship Coordinator, Dean, Vice President for Academic Affairs, Vice President for Research and Innovation, International Relations Officer, Director for International Linkages, College International Linkages Coordinator, Student Council Adviser, Student Affairs Coordinator, Student Publication Moderator, and GAD Focal Person.

Research Instrument

The research instruments that were used in this study consisted of a questionnaire and an interview guide.

Questionnaire. This is an adapted survey questionnaire from Katigbak and Amante (2019). The questionnaire is composed of three parts; Part One pertained to the items for determining the profile of the respondents. A.) For the students, the following were determined; i.) year level and ii.) degree and major taken. B.) For the teachers, information about their i.) degree program taught, ii.) course/s taught, iii.) academic qualification and iv.) number of years in the service. And for the administrators, that include the i.) position, ii.) academic qualification, and iii.) number of years in the service.

Part Two contains questions about the action lines for ASED and the extent of its implementation and Part Three is about the queries with regard to the challenges encountered in the implementation of the action lines.

The researcher sought the expertise of the faculty-researchers and Teacher Education students to test the validity of the instrument. They evaluated the contents and criteria set in the instrument. Validators are educators who are expert in the field relevant to this study and are engaged in conducting various researches.

Interview Guide. A structured interview guide was prepared for easy and smooth flow of the interview process and ensured that all necessary information are captured from the participants. This is a series of open-ended questions utilized during interviews to validate the information received from the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the authorities before distributing the instrument for the study. The administration of the questionnaires was done by the researcher in a face to face manner.

The researcher also conducted the face-to-face Key Informant Interview (KII) to the five (5) key informants composed of students and faculty/administrator from each institution, studying and teaching in the College of Education and handling subjects in BSEd and BEED programs, respectively. Interview responses were recorded using the note taking and video recording methods. After the collection of data, identifying information was removed to ensure the informants' anonymity and confidentiality of the data and is only accessible by the researcher. A unique number was assigned to every informant. All responses were documented, thus the researcher organized and analyze the qualitative data into major categories which are based from the interview questions.

KII is in accordance with the concepts of triangulation method, wherein, it involves multiple datasets and investigations to address the objectives of this study. Through this method, it enhances the validity and credibility of the findings.

Data Analysis

The following were used in the treatment of data:

1. Frequency Count – This descriptive statistic was employed to describe the following; 1) profile of the respondents in terms of: a) year level; b) degree and major taken; c) degree program and course taught; d) academic qualification; e) position; and f) number of years in the service.
2. Weighted Mean – Was used to describe the extent of implementation of the action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED and the challenges encountered in its implementation. The formula was:

$$W = \frac{\Sigma fx}{\Sigma f}$$

where:

W = Weighted Mean

Σfx = sum of all products of f and x

f = frequency of each weight

x = weight

Σf = sum of all frequency on each item

3. Ranking of the results was also employed in terms of the extent of implementation and challenges encountered in the implementation of the action lines.
4. Likert scale was used to determine the extent of implementation and the challenges encountered by the respondents.

The extent of implementation of the action lines and the challenges encountered in the implementation were measured using a 4-point scale as follows:

Scale	Description
3.25 – 4.00	Highly Implemented (HI) -when the characteristics manifested is very extensively demonstrated.
2.50 – 3.24	Moderately Implemented (MI) -moderately demonstrated and frequently produces the desired results.
1.75 – 2.49	Slightly Implemented (SI) - sometimes demonstrated and fairly produces desired results.
1.00 – 1.74	Not Implemented (NI) - is rarely or not at all demonstrated and does not produce the desired result.

Ethical Considerations

These were primarily required to guide the researcher on the research designs and practices to be undertaken.

Honesty and Objectivity. Utmost integrity in gathering the data, reporting the results, and sustaining unprejudiced all throughout the study was observed by the researcher.

Intellectual Property Rights. A formal letter was sent to the HEIs to request for the conduct of the study and permission on the perusal of records pertaining to ASEAN-related activities and participation of its faculty and students during the face-to-face interviews. In addition, all references used were cited and acknowledged.

Voluntary Participation. A written consent was secured from both the respondents and the participants to ensure that their participation is voluntary, and information revealed were treated anonymously and confidentially. Voluntary that

they may opt not to answer questions which they think offensive or intimately personal, and withdraw at any stage of the data gathering process.

Informed consent. The participants were provided with an orientation regarding the objectives of the study, their rights as volunteers, as well as the potential risks and advantages associated with their involvement. The individuals were asked to provide their autographs as a means of indicating their endorsement.

Respect for Data Privacy. Identities and responses of the participating HEIs, administrators, faculty, and student respondents and participants remained anonymous throughout the study.

Confidentiality. Information collected from the questionnaire, interview, and secondary sources of data such as records of activities were treated with utmost confidentiality and kept protected that these can only be accessible to the researcher.

Chapter IV

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

This chapter presents the overall results and findings of the study, which primarily focused on the determination and assessment of the action lines in ASED Priority Area 1.3, as well as the problems faced during implementation.

Action Lines Implemented in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP

ASEAN Work Plan on Education 2016–2020 which was approved at the 9th ASEAN Education Ministers Meeting in 2016, has guided ASEAN Member States V(AMS), the ASEAN Secretariat (ASEC), and ASEAN entities and partners in developing and implementing regional initiatives on education. In line with this, the respondent HEIs particularly the College of Education offering Teacher Education Programs adhered to this end.

As shown in Table 3, action lines implemented by the HEIs anchored Priority Area 1.3 of ASED Work plan are consisting of; a) student/faculty mobility, b) webinar/seminar/training/lecture activities in collaboration with ASEAN Member States, c) conferences/ fora/ congress initiated and participated, d) international credit transfer program, and e) utilization of modules in required subject which is ASEAN integration and other subject integrating the ASEAN-related topic.

Student/ Faculty mobility

The College of Development Education (CDE) in HEI3 welcomed Indonesian student-teachers of the Southeast Asian (SEA) Teacher Project or the “Pre-Service Student Teacher Exchange in Southeast Asia” on January 22, 2018.

Table 3

Action Lines implemented in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP of the Selected Public HEIs in Camarines Sur

	Action lines	Date
1. Student/ Faculty mobility	1.1 Southeast Asian (SEA) Teacher Project or "Pre-Service Student Teacher Exchange in Southeast Asia"	January 22, 2018
	1.2 SEA- Teacher Program 2019- 4 Indonesian Pre-Service Teachers	January 18, 2019
	1.3 SEAMEO-SEA Teacher Project 2019 (8th Batch)	September 2, 2019
	1.4 Collaborative Evaluation of CDE's Student Internship Abroad Program (SIAP) 2019	October 1-4, 2019
2. Webinar/ Seminar/ training/ lecture activities in collaboration with ASEAN Member States	2.1 CBSUA-UMK Joint-International Seminar on Academic, Economic and Cultural Undertakings (JISAECU) 2019	November 4-6, 2019
	2.2 Joint International Webinar on Academic, Economic and Cultural Undertaking (JIWAECU) 2020	August 19, 2020
	2.3 CBSUA-UHAMKA Guest Lecturer Exchange	November 2020
	2.4 International Webinar Workshop on Assessment in the New Educational Landscape	February 19, 2021
	2.5 International Leadership Webinar	March 19, 2021
	2.6 Virtual Guest Lecture Series- Education (TPACK on Education and Character Education)	August 24-25, 2021
	2.7 International Organizational Management and Educational Leadership in the New Normal	October 13, 2021
	2.8 Fakultas Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Negeri Surabaya - King Mongkuts University of Technology North Bangkok (FIP UNESA-KMUTNB) Summer Camp (FKBSC)	August 2022
	2.9 Training-Workshop on Digital Tools for Education	July 8, 2022

	Action lines	Date
	2.10 Webinar on Overcoming Challenges in Blended and Online Learning Environment	September 9, 2022
	2.11 Project TUKDO	October 2022
3. Conferences/ Forums/ Congress	3.1 1st ACSET and 2nd ACCESS	October 26-27, 2020
	3.2 International Webinar Forum 2022- Digital Age in Social Media Era	March 2022
4. Credit Transfer Program	4.1 International Credit Transfer Program	September 22, 2020
5. Module in ASEAN integration and other subject with integration of ASEAN-related topics	5.1 Utilization of modules in Required subject- ASEAN integration and other subject integrating the ASEAN-related topic	August 2018

This project aimed to promote regional cooperation in education and cultural exchange in HEI3 and Indonesia. SEA-Teacher Project began in HEI3 by sending student-interns from their university to ASEAN Member countries such as Indonesia for intercultural and academic engagement and internship programs. Indonesian student-interns were assigned in the campuses of HEI3 for their internship while having a series of activities to attend to for the project.

HEI3 also led the send-off of the outbound students who went to Indonesia for the said project. After a month, students gained knowledge and meaningful experiences to be shared as they returned in their university. Earlier of the same year, four (4) Indonesian Pre-Service Teachers of SEA-Teacher Program met the HEI3 university president as their courtesy call and start of the exchange program.

Student mobility is defined by Junor and Usher (2008), the OECD (2009), and UNESCO (2009) as students who leave their home nations to study in another. According to Rexeisen et al. (2008), student mobility improves graduate employability, enables technological and intellectual transfer, and increases cultural

awareness, all of which promote regional integration in both economic and political terms. Despite these benefits, Soejatminah (2018) remarked that while there are several studies investigating student mobility patterns, research on the potentially transformative effects of regional mobility networks is sparse. Nonetheless, ASEAN University (AUN) was devoted to increasing student mobility in the area and can thus be viewed as a deliberative space capable of promoting student mobility. According to the findings of his research, AUN has built regional quality certification and credit transfer mechanisms to facilitate credit student mobility among AUN member universities. In this sense, the implementation of the Indonesian qualification framework has strengthened AUN's operationalization of the credit transfer system between member universities.

Meanwhile, a faculty from HEI3 visited and represented the university at Neerada School in Vientiane, Laos on October 1-4, 2019 during the Collaborative Evaluation of Student Internship Abroad Program (SIAP) to monitor the SIAP and strengthen faculty engagement in cultural and academic endeavors related to Student internship.

Webinar/ seminar/ training/ lecture activities in collaboration with ASEAN Member States

Faculty from Universitas Muria Kudus (UMK) in Indonesia visited the HEI3 for their UMK Joint-International Seminar on Academic, Economic and Cultural Undertakings (JISAECU) 2019 on November 2019. Partnership with UMK commenced during the SEAMEO SEA Teacher Project in January 2019. The joint conference sought to deliver high-quality worldwide knowledge exchange focused on educational development, enabling, while encouraging services to effectively respond to educational requirements and concerns. programs and activities for

sustaining long-term economic growth; and promote cultural values and meanings of ASEAN member countries.

In addition, as part of the Joint International Webinar on Academic, Economic, and Cultural Undertakings (JIWAECU), HEI3 and UMK launched the International Academic Engagement on August 19, 2020. This was part of the various programs in the MOU on Academic Engagement activities consist of the following: (1) Establishment of International Center (2) Virtual Student Exchange Program (3) Virtual Faculty Exchange Program (4) Student Virtual Engagement Activities (5) Joint International Webinar for Teachers and (5) International Research Collaboration.

Commencing the JIWAECU 2020 was its series of webinars with Joint International Webinar on Education: Pedagogical Approaches in Teaching during the time of Covid-19 Pandemic on August 26 2020. Webinar Series #1- “Increasing Profit in Swine Production using the Same Inputs” on August 26, 2020. Webinar Series #2 Education hosted by UMK highlighted the topic on Empowering parents’ involvement, strengthening support system for children held on September 23, 2020. Faculty members from HEI3 discussed the parents’ vital roles in ensuring enrichment of their children’s lives in time of pandemic. Said webinars were hosted by HEI3 in partnership with UMK to sustain international linkage with known universities in addressing the challenges of Fourth Industrial Revolution and Education 4.0 amidst pandemic.

Collaboration between HEI3 - College of Development Education (CDE) and Faculty of Teacher Education (Fakultas Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan-FKIP)- Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. Hamka (UHAMKA), Indonesia commenced with the Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) Signing in November 4, 2019. Part of the said MOA is the continuing partnership including Guest Lecturer Exchange that

began with Series 1: Educational Management with the CDE Dean serving as guest lecturer of Primary Education Department, Social Science Education, Natural Science Education and Mathematics Education Department on School-based Management System in the Philippine Setting on December 10, 2020. The said collaboration is in support of the Internationalization initiatives of the University President thru the Office of Vice President for Business and External Affairs (OVPBEA).

Moreover, Guest Lecturer Exchange 2020 intensively focused on the topic, Administration and Supervision as Series #2 held on December 16, 2020. Guest lecturer was the faculty member of the College of Development Education in HEI3. This endeavor was part of the collaboration between HEI3 – CDE and FKIP-UHAMKA, Indonesia.

It was also noted from the respondents that the League of Pre-Service Elementary Educators (LPEE) of the College of Education from HEI3 in partnership with Universitas Muria Kudus, Indonesia sponsored the International Webinar Workshop on Assessment in the New Educational Landscape on February 19, 2021. Also, an International Leadership Webinar during the Educators' Week 2021 was also conducted by the College of Education- Student Council in partnership with Universitas Mataram, Indonesia on March 19, 2021. More so, the Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar (PGSD) FKIP UHAMKA also initiated a Virtual Guest Lecture Series with talks on Education specifically about TPACK on Education and Character Education wherein the invited lecturers came from the Philippines, and attended by UHAMKA students enrolled in the Primary Education Program, from August 24-25, 2021.

Further, HEI3 in cooperation with Universitas Muria Kudus (UMK) and Universitas Mataram (UNRAM) partnered in the International Organizational Management and Educational Leadership in the New Normal on 13 October 2021. The international training featured renowned resource speakers from the Philippines and Indonesia, who interactively discussed Organizational Management in the Philippine Setting and in Indonesian context and experiences. Educational Leadership in Philippine setting and how the Indonesian universities adapted to changes and challenges to answer the current situation during the pandemic was few of the other topics conferred.

The HEI1 in partnership with the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology, and Universitas Negeri Surabaya offered an online Fakultas Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Negeri Surabaya - King Mongkuts University of Technology North Bangkok (FIP UNESA-KMUTNB) Summer Camp (FKBSC) Course 2022. This was composed of 28 hours of lecture course, 18 hours of individual essay, 12 hours of individual summary, and 2 hours of group project and presentation with a total of 40 hours equivalent to 6 credits. There were 12 learning courses offered which include the following; 1) Education: A Digital technology, 2) Technology Builds Culture, 3) Disability Inclusion in College, 4) Ethno-Steam Education at Elementary School, and 5) Problem of Classroom Management.

Students and faculty from HEI2 also involved in Training-Workshop on Digital Tools for Education conducted by the COEd student council via zoom-meeting on July 8, 2022. The goals of the activity were as follows; to increase students' and teachers' knowledge regarding digital tools for education, to consolidate and share information about the appropriate usage of digital tools, and promote the benefits of using digital tools in the online learning.

Webinar on Overcoming Challenges in Blended and Online Learning Environment conducted last September 9, 2022 was supervised by the COEd student council in partnership with Central Organization for Role-Driven Educators (CORE), HEI2 Federation of Student Councils, YOUTeach-Philippines Bicol, YOUTeach MIMAROPA as part of the internationalization initiatives of HEI2 and Vongchavalitkul University. This online learning webinar aimed to make the new normal of learning more appreciative and interactive, promoted the benefits and advantages of learning online while also being able to have fun with virtual activities, and raised cognizance that online learning will be apprehended effectively even when compared to face-to-face learning.

Conversely, the College of Education in HEI2 have various programs and projects supporting their institutions' goal of generating sustainable linkages or partnerships in the global context and achieve their aim, that is to internationalize their institution. Project TUKDO with international speakers from Vongchavalitkul University in Thailand, the Teacher Tree Myanmar, Angat Pinoy Japan and lecturers from other countries including teachers in Dubai, United Arab Emirates and other well-known international university in the Philippines like the De La Salle University partnered with HEI2. This project also reached Thailand and Myanmar. Aside from attending, participants were also willing to co-host the same initiative in their respective countries as they have seen the impact it may bring to their institutions.

COE faculty and administrators of HEI2 are currently undergoing dialogue with organizations like Batik Bakau in Indonesia and Kuala Tenganu in Malaysia for initiatives on environment protection, Ministry of Youth and Sports in Indonesia, and Ministry of Youth in Cambodia for youth engagement and women empowerment initiatives. Moreover, the COE student council held for the second time the Young

Teachers Empowering Approach as Community Helpmates (YouTEACH) Program 2.2 with the rallying call “The Pentagoals,” with the core focus on PENTAGOALS: Project Serene (SDG 16), Project Sentinel (SDG 15), Project Tukdo (SDG 4), Project Aid (SDG3), and Project Parity (SDG 10). These were the five fundamental domains of the Sustainable Development Goals.

Conferences/ forums/ congress initiated and participated

Global Learning Collaboration Project between Universitas Mataram, Indonesia and HEI3 created an opportunity for research enthusiasts as the two universities hosted the two conferences held at the same date, the 2nd Annual Conference on Education and Social Sciences (2nd ACCESS) and 1st Annual Conference on Science, Education, and Technology (1st ACSET) on October 26-27, 2020. The Dean of the College of Development Education and Research Director of HEI3 served as resource speakers in the conferences and the faculty members of CDE also participated in the research paper presentations. This initiative was part of the internationalization program HEI3. The internationalization of higher education refers to the incorporation of an international or intercultural aspect into the many components of an educational institution, including teaching, research, and service. This definition is derived from the work of Jane Knight and the International Association of Universities in 2006, as cited by Zolfaghari et al. in 2009. Knight and de Wit (1995), as referenced by Zolfaghari et al. (2009), have identified four distinct categories for the reasons behind internationalization: political, economic, academic, and socio-cultural. The rationale behind the academic purpose is closely tied to the improvement of the teaching and learning process, as well as the pursuit of excellence in research and scholarly endeavors. The socio-cultural rationale for internationalization is undergoing transformation in response to the potential

ramifications of globalization. Historically, higher education has been an integral component of cultural accords and reciprocal interactions.

Respondents were also encouraged to attend or join endeavors from the invitation of other ASEAN Member States (AMS). In the interview conducted, respondent-students from HEI1 shared their experiences recently when they joined the Student Council of Early Childhood Education of the Universitas Negeri Surabaya in their International Webinar Forum 2022 with the topic on Digital Age in Social Media Era. This opened an opportunity for them to be aware of the impact of digital technology as it transformed the globe, according to UNICEF. As more youngsters have access to the internet, its impact to childhood will increase. According to them, one of the significant learnings from the forum was on how to be a responsible social media user to strike a balance between the youngsters' freedom to access information and their development into mature young adults.

International Credit Transfer Program

CDE of the HEI3 in cooperation with the Office of Vice President for Academic Affairs (OVPA) and Office of the Vice President for Business and External Affairs (OVPEA) launched the International Credit Transfer Program (ICTP) with Universitas Muria Kudus (UMK), Indonesia. This is a program of academic courses that are available to enable students to complete the regular requirements for a teacher education program. The two universities closed ties as regards partnership in research, instruction, and linkages. The said program encompasses the Academic and Cultural Exchange Program where UMK students will experience cultural and academic engagements with HEI3. Processes involved in the Transfer Program include the curriculum mapping wherein both the partner universities shall ensure that the subjects to be taken by the students have similar course description.

Students from HEI3 will be enrolled in subjects at UMK, likewise the students from UMK. This certain course will be taken within one semester for 5 months. In Batch 1, 1st semester school year 2020-2021, there were 5 students from HEI3 and 5 students from UMK as exchange students involved in the Transfer Program. The mode of instruction in both universities in batch 1 was pure online, 75 % synchronous and 25% asynchronous or through the Virtual Learning Portal. The grade of the instructor from the course taken by the students in a certain course at the UMK will be credited to the course wherein they were enrolled in HEI3, and vice versa.

In an interview, respondent asserted that scheduling of the course was one of the problems they encountered during the program and resolved by setting an arrangement by seeking the most favorable and available schedule for both the universities.

Mutual credit and degree recognition are the most important pieces in the harmonization process. The scope of mutual credit and degree recognition covers education qualifications at every level, including credit earned from foreign education institutions and professional and academic titles conferred in foreign country (Butter, 2006; Hawkins, 2012, Teichler, 2011).

Utilization of modules in Required Subject-ASEAN integration and other subject integrating the ASEAN-related topics

ASEAN integration is a required subject with 3 credit units taken up by the students in BSEd and BEED programs of HEI3. Module was crafted by the faculty members handling the subject. This required course aims to develop the students' skills, knowledge, and understanding of the best practices in the education of the different universities in the ASEAN region. It is a regional community approach to the

integration of education through field exposure or a foreign language study that will create more joint academic programs and partnerships with other universities responsive to meeting the needs of 21st-century learners.

HEI1 and HEI3 integrate ASEAN concepts in some of their subject offerings such as in Linguistics, Literature, The Contemporary World, Social Studies, Asian Studies, and World History.

Extent of Implementation of Action Lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP

Findings revealed the respondents' adjudications along the implementation of various action lines in priority area 1.3 of the ASEAN Work Plan in Education (ASED) in their Teacher Education Program (Table 4). Generally, the selected public Higher Education Institutions in the province of Camarines Sur have initiated and implemented these action lines as disclosed in the results gathering an over all mean rating of 3.37 and interpreted as Highly Implemented.

Conduct conferences/ seminars/ fora on ASEAN

Respondents affirmed that their school conducts conferences/ seminars/ fora related to ASEAN, yielding the highest degree of implementation with the mean rating of 3.66, Highly Implemented (HI). The activities outlined in this action line, which were previously explained in relation to Objective 1, align with the findings of Katigbak and Amante's (2019) study. The report posits that higher education is expected to play a crucial role in fostering regional socio-cultural development and addressing the gaps in development among member countries. To achieve these objectives, it is crucial for higher education institutions to foster human capital and build a unified framework for higher education systems (ASEAN Secretariat, 2008b, 2009a).

Table 4

Extent of Implementations of Actions Lines in Priority Area 1.3 of ASED in Selected HEIs offering Teacher Education Programs

Action Lines	HEIs			M	I	Rank
	1	2	3			
1. Conduct conferences/ seminars/ forums on ASEAN.	3.91	3.49	3.59	3.66	HI	1
2. Support ASEAN in Today's World Program.	3.73	3.48	3.49	3.57	HI	2
3. Develop long-term plan to institutionalize the ASEAN Studies courses as evidenced by a complete set of teaching materials for ASEAN Studies.	3.45	3.40	3.59	3.48	HI	3
4. Develop ASEAN regionalism flagship research programs.	3.64	3.38	3.39	3.47	HI	4
5. Develop guidelines for cross-border mobility of students and scholars on ASEAN Studies.	3.45	3.27	3.61	3.44	HI	5
6. Implement guidelines for cross-border mobility of faculty on ASEAN Studies.	3.36	3.26	3.44	3.35	HI	6
7. Develop/expand the ASEAN Foundation's initiative to implement Model ASEAN Program.	3.45	3.15	3.41	3.34	HI	7
8. Implement guidelines for cross-border mobility of students and scholars on ASEAN Studies.	3.18	3.31	3.51	3.33	HI	8
9. Develop guidelines for cross-border mobility of faculty on ASEAN Studies.	3.27	3.32	3.41	3.33	HI	9
10. Utilizes ASEAN Studies modules and Instructional Manual and made available to university students and educators.	3.18	3.27	3.44	3.30	HI	10.5
11. Develop guidelines for ASEAN Studies courses (identify structure of ASEAN Studies courses to serve as basis for recognition of an ASEAN Studies courses.	3.36	3.14	3.39	3.30	HI	10.5
12. Implement various scholarship programs on ASEAN.	3.45	3.11	3.29	3.28	HI	12.5
13. Update the ASEAN Studies modules and Instructional Manual and made available to university students and educators.	3.27	3.25	3.32	3.28	HI	12.5
14. Conduct survey of existing ASEAN Studies courses.	2.91	2.97	3.29	3.06	MI	14
OVERALL MEAN	3.40	3.27	3.44	3.37	HI	

Legend: HEIs – Higher Education Institutions
M – Mean
I - Interpretation

Interpretation:
3.25 – 4.00 - Highly Implemented (MI)
2.50 – 3.24 - Moderately Implemented (MI)
1.75 – 2.49 - Slightly Implemented (SI)
1.00 – 1.74 - Not Implemented (NI)

Educators who attended the conferences/ seminars/ fora on ASEAN were benefitted in terms of improving communications skills, renewing motivation and confidence, gaining expert knowledge especially in terms of ASEAN-related topic, and networking with others. Furthermore, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has launched the faculty development project. The concept was established based on the premise that the caliber of faculty members plays a crucial role in determining the standard of both general and vocational education. Improving the caliber of high school educators is expected to positively impact the standard of secondary education, thereby ensuring that students possess the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in higher education (Coursehero, 2023). Furthermore, the ASEAN Secretariat report on the ASEAN State of Education specifically highlights the significance of education as the primary pillar of support for the ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community (ASCC). In accordance with its designated role, the ASCC is tasked with the responsibility of guaranteeing that the labor force within the ASEAN region is adequately equipped and advantaged by the process of economic integration. This objective is to be achieved by the allocation of increased resources towards fundamental and advanced education, training, as well as the development of science and technology. These efforts are guided by the principles outlined in the Declaration of ASEAN Concord II. The ASCC provides a comprehensive overview of education as it recognizes that the cultivation and improvement of human resources play a crucial role in promoting employment opportunities, reducing poverty rates, addressing socio-economic inequalities, and fostering equitable economic growth. Hence, activities for this action line are only few of the many innovations supporting ASCC's goals.

Support ASEAN in Today's World Program

Along with the aspiration of establishing partnerships for international linkages and promoting internationalization initiatives which have been strengthened by the different above mentioned endeavors, respondents also affirmed the Highly Implemented Support for ASEAN in Today's World Program (M= 3.57).

ASEAN in Today's World (AsTW) is a fortnight-long global educational initiative that centers on the exploration of ASEAN and East Asian matters. This program is specifically tailored to cater to undergraduate students enrolled in universities worldwide. The primary medium of instruction for the courses is English. The introduction of AsTW took place in March 2009 within the country of Thailand. The period spanning from 2009 to 2011 witnessed the collaborative organization of the Asia Science and Technology Workshop (AsTW) by Kyushu University in Japan and Mahidol University in Thailand. Between 2012 and 2014, Kyushu University collaborated with Ateneo de Manila University in the Philippines to organize and hold the Asia-Pacific Student Workshop (AsTW) in the aforementioned country. The AsTW conference was hosted at Vietnam National University, Hanoi (Vietnam) between 2015 and 2017. The AsTW sessions were conducted at the University of Malaya (Malaysia) between 2018 and 2020. The curriculum was done in an online format from 2021 to 2022 as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. It was a collaborative effort between Kyushu University and Mahidol University. The on-site location for the event in 2023 has been designated as the campus of Mahidol University.

The AsTW program, supported by the ASEAN Secretariat and ASEAN University Network (AUN), involves the collaboration of six esteemed universities in the ASEAN regions and Japan. These universities include the University of Malaya,

Mahidol University, Ateneo de Manila University, Vietnam National University, Hanoi, Fukuoka Women's University, and Kyushu University (AsTW, 2023).

The findings of the interview indicated that the participants exhibited a lack of awareness regarding the ASEAN in Today's World Program. The findings of this study provide support for Jayaraman's (2017) assertion that there is a lack of awareness regarding ASEAN among its own populace. The author underscored the importance of enhancing awareness among residents of ASEAN Member States (AMS) regarding the relevance of establishing a community centered around ASEAN. The findings of Thompson and Thianthai's (2007) study indicate that the level of awareness and knowledge regarding ASEAN varied across different countries. Specifically, Vietnam, Laos, Brunei, and Indonesia exhibited the highest levels of awareness and knowledge, while Singapore and the Philippines shown comparatively lower levels. It was observed that in 2007, the level of awareness and understanding of ASEAN in the Philippines was comparatively lower than that of other member countries within the ASEAN region.

Although the respondent HEIs and their respective students do not partake or unaware of the AsTW Program, they demonstrated cooperation and support in other ways such as the faculty and students' attendance to seminars/trainings (HEI1, HEI2, HEI3), student mobility/ exchange program in ASEAN Member States (AMS) (HEI3), and integration of ASEAN concepts in instructional delivery (HEI1, HEI2, HEI3). These HEIs were in acquiescence with the requirement of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) for the need to shift education from input-based to outcome-based where the center of planning is the students to address the demands and challenges of the ASEAN community and/or the international community (SEAMEO-INNOTECH, 2020).

Develop long-term plan to institutionalize the ASEAN Studies courses

Long term plan is evidenced by a complete set of teaching materials for ASEAN Studies ranked 3 and assessed to be Highly Implemented (M=3.48). In the interview, participant in HEI3 shared positions with regard to this action line that

Our university officials together with the whole university community were united in upholding the ASEAN Community vision through their continued support to the organizations' programs and community-building efforts. Learning materials such as modules and course syllabus catering the content, issues and concerns regarding educational landscape of the ASEAN Member States and other relevant topics were being used and taught to the students as part of their learning courses.

In HEI2, the "ASEAN Magazine" issued by the regional organization had been issued and promoted by the respondent to the public specially to their students for use. The ASEAN Magazine aimed to share and communicate ASEAN's works to its citizens.

Conduct survey of existing ASEAN Studies courses

On the other hand, 1) conducting a survey of existing ASEAN Studies courses was the least among the action lines with mean of 3.06 (Moderately Implemented). Succeeding were 2) update the ASEAN Studies modules and instructional manual and made available to university students and educators and 3) implement various scholarships programs on ASEAN both garnering a mean of 3.28 but still Highly Implemented. These imply that action lines necessitated an exuberant attention from HEIs to streamline learning opportunities and skills development for students, latest pedagogical skills for faculty, and mobilizing resources for education in relation to ASEAN Studies courses.

Findings revealed that respondents foundered to conduct survey of the ASEAN Studies courses, the 1st from the least implemented action line in priority area 1.3 of ASED with 3.06 mean rating and interpreted as Moderately Implemented.

All of the respondent HEIs planned to initiate undertakings relative to ASEAN but disclosed conducting survey about ASEAN Studies courses at present not as equal priority as the others. According to HEI2, there is a need for their institution to primarily mobilize internationalization initiatives and secure for administrative support specially that Teacher Education programs in their institution are less prioritized.

Similarly, HEI1 requires adept strategies to establish ASEAN awareness in their institution. This was evident during the interview when a participant conceded absence of knowledge about ASEAN. Hence, the institution must lead the integration of ASEAN in the teaching and learning experiences of their students to promote better organizational cognizance. While among the three institutions, HEI3 exemplified advance engagements in terms of action lines in ASED, however, no evidence was accessible in terms of conducting survey about ASEAN Studies courses to capture the views and perspectives of students, opinion-makers, policy-makers, thought-leaders and other stakeholders of the institution. This implies that the respondent institutions need to set out the aims and purposes of ASEAN to accelerate its awareness within and beyond its community.

Update the ASEAN Studies modules and Instructional Manual and made available to university students and educators

Ranked 12.5 yet Highly Implemented action line for priority area 1.3 of ASED with mean rating of 3.28. HEI3 offered ASEAN Integration as a required subject in Teacher Education both in secondary and elementary programs. As their practice, the subject's content and pedagogy is being revised and /or updated to keep their students attuned with the latest concepts, innovations, and trends in ASEAN.

Despite the non-inclusion of a specific subject for ASEAN, HEI1 and HEI2 managed to incorporate the organization's vision and aspirations in their classroom

instruction through amalgamation in allied subjects as mentioned in previous discussions. HEI1, HEI2, and HEI3 provided the course syllabi, modules, and other instructional materials such as PowerPoint presentations and reading articles to their students.

The regional organization did not only seek students' awareness in tertiary level students but also aimed to foster ASEAN awareness and identity among elementary and secondary students. According to the ASEAN Curriculum Assessment Project Report, which was given by the United States Agency International Development (USAID) in 2009, the ASEAN Member States (AMS) are actively engaged in endeavors to incorporate education on ASEAN and its constituent countries into their respective curricula. The proposal was jointly developed by the facility and the ASEAN Secretariat with the objective of collecting and evaluating primary and secondary school textbooks and other educational resources related to ASEAN that are currently being utilized in the Member States. This initiative serves as an essential initial measure towards the creation of supplementary materials that aim to cultivate a higher level of awareness regarding ASEAN among primary and secondary school students and young individuals within the ASEAN Member States (AMS). It has been widely reported that the inclusion of ASEAN-related content is primarily observed in the social studies and history curricula. However, there have been occasional references or integration of such information in disciplines such as art, music, economics, and natural sciences. This suggests that there is more potential for effectively involving students in ASEAN-related topics.

Implement various scholarship programs on ASEAN

Also ranked 12.5, nonetheless, Highly Implemented action line with mean rating of 3.28. HEI1, HEI2, and HEI3 were compliant of Republic Act 10931 otherwise known as Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education. An “act promoting universal access to quality tertiary education by providing free tuition and other school fees in State Universities and Colleges, Local Universities and Colleges, and State-Run Technical-Vocational Institutions, establishing the Tertiary Education Subsidy and Student Loan Program, strengthening the Unified Student Financial Assistance System for Tertiary Education, and appropriating fund therefore”. The government agency responsible for the implementation of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act (RA 10931) is known as the Unified Student Financial Assistance System for Tertiary Education, commonly referred to as UniFAST. The legal framework and the University Financial Assistance System (UniFAST) collectively aim to ensure that worthy individuals in the Philippines are provided with fair and equal access to educational opportunities. However, the three higher education institutions (HEIs) that were surveyed confirmed that they do not currently provide any scholarship programs specifically targeted towards the ASEAN region.

Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Action Lines for ASED in Teacher Education Program

Some challenges are faced by the Higher Education Institutions in implementing programs/ activities related to ASED. The challenges encountered were the following: 1) family financial constraints, 2) unavailable resources (home-related), 3) school financial constraints, 4) student’s well-being/health condition, 5.5)

insufficient/unavailable school facilities, and 5.5) students unqualified for the exchange programs.

Table 5

Ranking of the Challenges encountered in the Implementation of Action Lines for ASEd in Selected HEIs Offering Teacher Education Programs

Challenges encountered	RANKING			Initial Rank	Final Rank
	1	2	3		
1. Family financial constraints	1	1	1	3	1 st
2. Unavailable resources (home-related)	2	2	2	6	2 nd
3. School Financial constraints	3	3	3	9	3 rd
4. Student's well-being/health condition	7.5	5	4	16.5	4 th
5. Insufficient/ unavailable school resources/facilities	5	8	6	19	5.5 th
6. Students unqualified for Exchange program	6	6	7	19	5.5 th
7. Students' interests towards the activities	10.5	4	5	19.5	7 th
8. Absence of ASEAN-related courses in the TE Curriculum	4	11	10.5	25.5	8 th
9. Unsupportive parents	7.5	7	13	27.5	9 th
10. Unsupportive, attitude, beliefs of faculty	9	9	8	26	10 th
11. Unsupportive school administrators	10.5	10	9	29.5	11 th
12. Faculty did not meet the qualifications and skills required for Exchange program	12	12	10.5	34.5	12 th
13. School do not recognize ASEAN-related activities or celebrations	13	13	12	38	13 th

Legend:

HEIs – Higher Education Institutions

Family financial constraints

Parents or family is one of the most significant partners in learning and promoting the overall educational goals of the school. The involvement of parents is a crucial factor in determining the effectiveness of an education system. According to Llego (2023), empirical evidence supports the notion that the implementation of this intervention yields positive outcomes such as enhanced academic performance,

decreased rates of absenteeism and attrition, and an overall improvement in the educational standards. However, the financial burden of education placed a substantial economic strain on university students (Montalto, et al., 2018 as referenced in Sabri, et al., 2020). When family was confronted with financial challenges, it made difficult for them to get involved and support their children's education. Thus, survey revealed family's financial constraints to be the most encountered challenge (ranked 1) among the three public HEIs in Camarines Sur.

It was noted that family's income is being allocated for food, bills, children's needs in school, and other basic living necessities. Absence of students exuded impact on how the school will shape their planning and delivering plans towards making good progress over their ASED-related programs and activities. During the interview, participant asserted:

Parents are supportive with the university's projects and programs but the problem is the insufficiency of our students' family in terms of financial. Our students can be classified under average economic status. So, probably students were qualified but unable to join because of family's financial problem. But we also have some students who are financially capable but not all.

In congruence, participant from HEI2 divulged:

Students belong to class B and C so even if they are qualified for the student exchange program, still some of them cannot afford to participate or their parents do not allow them to join because of financial problems in the family. Because aside from the financial support given by the university, students also need to have the allowance coming from them.

Another participant from HEI2 also disclosed:

The students here, if to be assessed, most of the enrollees were in middle to less fortunate. Am I right, that mobility of students is included in this program? So, if they do not have the resources and financial capacity, that could be a major factor for not joining.

Unavailable resources at home

Moreover, unavailable resources at home are on the second (2nd) rank from the challenges met by the respondents. Participants conveyed during the interview that this disparity in resources is one of the factors which exacerbated their academic performance and quality of learning. Cellular phones are merely used by the students during their synchronous classes while school requirements were being accomplished mostly in adjacent internet or computer shops. Affirming this constraint was the statement of the participant as quoted *“parents do not have the capacity to provide all their children’s needs. Some of our students were in the middle class only.”*

Another participant said, *“this problem is also connected with family financial constraints because if family is confronted with inadequacy in financial capacity, it’s possible that they cannot buy educational resources needed by their children.”* Certainly, availability of resources and the way they were spent influenced students’ learning opportunities (OECD, 2012).

School financial constraints

Third (3rd) challenge was school financial constraints. Deteriorating financial situation has a negative impact on the quality of education (Michel, 2006). According to a participant, *“there is limited number of resources in the school so the quality of the programs and activities will be sacrificed. There is also fund shortage. Faculty also experienced similar setback for their professional development.”*

One HEI stated that school funding were allotted for internationalization programs such as the Student Exchange program. Nonetheless, participating Teacher Education students were required to allot personal budget to suffice the financial needs for the entire duration of the program. Therefore, it is imperative that

students possess the necessary knowledge to make informed decisions that align with their financial well-being, taking into consideration the economic circumstances of both their educational institution and their family (World Bank, 2023). One participant also added:

CoEd is not a priority course of the university. According to the administration, budget allocation shall focus from the needs of service area. Because of prioritization of the programs and activities, and alignment of courses which are based from the vision of the university that is, the leading university in geology, bio-resource science, and environmental management, CoEd is less prioritize. Thus, even the business administration management courses were not part of the priority courses. So, when it comes to projects' implementation, prioritization comes in and CoEd projects were less prioritized.

In addition, another participant explained that *“school financial constraint is another problem, the budget allocation for ASEAN-related activities. Less budget is allotted for this kind of program.”*

Similarly, one participant further shared:

Problem with school financial constraints is during its process as well as the diversity in personnel interpretations. They have contradicting arguments in terms of services' beneficiary. Others would say we can avail this particular service but it would be precluded by the responsible office. Likewise, if there is no available budget, we cannot proceed. Also, if opportunity emanated in the middle of the school year, still, we cannot avail since it was not allocated.

Students' well-being/health condition

Another challenge in the successful implementation of ASED action lines is student's well-being/ health condition (ranked 4). A participant expressed his personal view that *“students' basic needs must be provided first as what have been stated in the Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs.”* According to Maslow's theory, human behavior is driven by a hierarchy of physiological and psychological requirements that evolve from fundamental to more intricate levels. According to Cherry (2022), the aforementioned hierarchy posits that individuals are driven to satisfy their fundamental needs prior to pursuing higher-level demands.

Insufficient/ unavailable school facilities

Insufficient/ unavailable facilities ranked 5.5. According to the participant,

Here in our institution, we experienced scantiness of classrooms which you can call as conducive for learning classrooms. Also, the issue of internet connectivity, it's really unstable. Hence, we were confronted with problem during online teaching and learning. Interactive boards were also indispensable in today's education system; the problem is we don't have enough number of it.

According to Smith, Higgins, Wal, and Miller (2005) and Onal and Demir (2017), as quoted by Rizwan et al. (2018), the Interactive White Board (IWB) is a pedagogical tool that fosters creative teaching, enables discussion, and motivates students in the process of acquiring information for educational purposes. Teachers can effectively cater to diverse learning styles by utilizing interactive features like as touch icons and a menu interface located on a toolbar. These features facilitate the display of notes and enable the presentation of learning materials on a digital board.

Students non-eligible for exchange program

Students non-eligible for exchange program also ranked 5.5. Participant specified that:

There are screening tests performed like interview, background checking, analyzing the students' profile, and if they were well-rounded students. Also, they should meet the academic standards of the partner university, and students should also be acquainted and actively participating in school event so they know how to manage their time during their curricular and extra-curricular activities.

According to the research conducted by Chao (2020), there is a notable disparity between intra-ASEAN student mobility and outward student mobility from ASEAN nations, with the former exhibiting much lower levels. This observation aligns with the findings of Chan (2012), who noted that many Asian countries see a significant outflow of students to Western nations. Consequently, a growing tendency

of regionalization or horizontal mobility of students within the Asian area is becoming apparent.

Accordingly, Chao (2020) proposed the establishment of a comprehensive intra-ASEAN mobility scheme that leverages the existing intra-ASEAN mobility schemes and draws inspiration from the advancements made in the European Erasmus mobility programs. The Erasmus program is an initiative established by the European Union with the aim of providing support for education, training, youth, and sport. With a projected budget of €26.2 billion for the year 2021, this program offers a multitude of options for more than 4 million individuals to engage in educational pursuits, training activities, experiential learning, and international volunteering experiences. The 2021-2027 program prioritizes social inclusion, the green and digital transitions, and the promotion of young people's engagement in political processes.

In addition to providing financial assistance, Erasmus+ also facilitates educational endeavors, scholarly investigations, collaborative networking, and policy discourse pertaining to European Union subjects. According to the European Commission (2023), the sports chapter aims to foster grassroots initiatives within the realm of sports.

Less encountered challenges

Listed below pertained to the less encountered challenges by the participant HEIs in the implementation of action lines which include, 7) students' interests towards the activities, 8) absence of ASEAN-related courses in the TE Curriculum, 9) unsupportive parents, 10) unsupportive, attitude, beliefs of faculty, 11) unsupportive school administrators, 12) faculty did not meet the qualifications and skills required

for exchange program, and 13) school does not recognize ASEAN-related activities or celebrations.

Other challenges encountered

It was also found out that HEIs also encountered other home-related factors. A participant admitted that *“the over-all disposition of the parents, their roles in supporting children’s learning in school affectively as well as being consistent when it comes to discipline affect implementation of activities.”* The research conducted by Bates, Deater-Deckard, Dodge, & Pettit (2003) demonstrated that the manner in which a child is disciplined has significant implications on their physical, behavioral, and psychological welfare. Similarly, their research on the attitudes of adolescents towards physical punishment revealed a prevailing perception among adolescents that physical forms of discipline are predominantly unfavorable. In households where parents have resorted to spanking, there is an increased probability that they will employ spanking as a disciplinary approach. The study moreover revealed that children hailing from households that employ corporal punishment as a disciplinary strategy exhibited a higher propensity to utilize and support physical punishment.

In addition, one participant was challenged by other school-related factor which were multiple roles, and other university activities such as accreditation.

According to the participant, he had multiple roles handled:

I am the internationalization point person in our college but I cannot perform well in this assignment because of so much responsibilities given to me. Aside from being the Internationalization Point Person, I also occupy the positions as student council adviser, student affairs coordinator, student publication moderator and university GAD Focal Person. Although it was in a collective manner, that I am not alone in preparing needed documents for the partnership project but again it was about having several responsibilities.

Participant further added that he is engaged to other university activities such as accreditation.

I have my proposal last year that my students will be engaged in student exchange, but it was accreditation and that our college need to concentrate in this pursuit. Now, we have plans to pursue the student mobility and my colleagues were willing to assist. But I was again given multiple designations and 18 units with 5 preparations. I really want to do this because this is my passion. I know I can make this happen supported by the track record and partnerships that we currently have but to these circumstances, its quite difficult. My student council officers are also very open and willing to attend in international exchanges because I was once a recipient of this and I want them to experience as well. Hence, what we do at present is we apply in Youth Community Leadership Initiative (YCLI) programs.

According to Carnevale (1992) and Clements-Croome (1997), as cited by Bushiri (2017), existing literature on the subject of multiple offices and office buildings suggests that factors such as employee dissatisfaction, cluttered workspaces, and the physical environment significantly contribute to decreased productivity among employees. According to Opperman (2002), the term "working environment" refers to the various processes, systems, structures, tools, or situations present in the workplace that can have either positive or negative effects on individual performance. The working environment encompasses various elements such as regulations, rules, culture, resources, working relationships, work location, and internal and external environmental factors. These aspects collectively impact the manner in which employees carry out their job responsibilities. According to Noble (2009), it is imperative to allocate greater focus towards the identification and management of the working environment. This is due to the fact that individuals who have negative perceptions of their surroundings may experience chronic stress.

Chapter V

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

Summary

The study assessed the implementation of action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for the ASEAN Work Plan on Education (ASED) in Teacher Education Program (TEP) of the selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Camarines Sur. Specifically, it shed lights to the following questions: 1) What are the action lines implemented in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP of the selected HEIs? 2) What is the extent of implementation of the action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED in TEP of the selected HEIs? and 3) What are the challenges encountered by the selected HEIs in the implementation of the action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED into their TEP?

The descriptive research method was used in this study. Respondents were the 359 4th year Teacher Education students and 93 faculty members/ administrators from three public Higher Education Institutions in the province of Camarines Sur. Obtained data using the questionnaire and interview were tallied, analyzed and interpreted using the frequency count, weighted mean, and ranking.

The findings were as follows:

The three HEIs have diverse action lines relative to ASED in TEP which include 1) student/ faculty mobility through the SEA Teacher Program and Collaborative Evaluation of Student Internship Abroad Program (SIAP), 2) webinar/ seminar /lecture activities in collaboration with ASEAN Member States (AMS), 3) conferences/ fora/ congress conducted and participated, 4) international credit transfer program, and 5) utilization of module in ASEAN integration and other subject with integration of ASEAN-related topics .

The three highest implemented programs/ activities were as follows; 1) the conduct of conferences/ seminars/ fora on ASEAN with mean rating of 3.66, HI, 2) support for ASEAN in Today's World Program with mean rating of 3.57, HI, and 3) develop long-term plan to institutionalize the ASEAN Studies courses as evidenced by a complete set of teaching materials for ASEAN Studies with mean rating of 3.48, HI.

Overall, this study showed that the action lines in priority area 1.3 of ASED in TEP were Highly Implemented with over all mean rating of 3.37.

The participants in the study identified three primary obstacles in the execution of action plans for the Advancement of Sustainable Education Development (ASED) within the Teacher Education Program (TEP): familial financial limitations, unavailability of home-related resources, and financial limits associated to schooling.

Conclusions

In terms of the action lines implemented by the selected HEIs, it could be concluded that:

1) Selected students in HEI 3 are engaged in student mobility, while the other HEIs strive to execute student/ faculty mobility in AMS; 2) HEIs initiated and participated in some trainings/ seminars conducted through online platforms in collaboration with AMS; 3) Students and faculty members from the three HEIs participated in conferences/ fora/ congress; 4) Only the HEI 3 has existing International Credit Transfer Program, while some respondents are less aware of the AMS programs/ activities in relation to ASED; and 5) HEI3 only has the required

subject being offered related to ASEAN, that is REQ- ASEAN Integration; while the two HEIs have integrated topics about ASEAN in some subjects being offered.

This study provided results as regard to the extent of implementation in the action lines and it was found out to be Highly implemented. Therefore, it could be concluded that: 1) The three HEIs were actively involved in implementing various ASED–related programs in their institutions, as manifested by the three highest implemented programs/ activities. 2) HEIs showed support in ASEAN’s goals and objectives by way of conducting conferences/ seminars/ fora about ASEAN. 3) Despite the knowledge-insufficiency about the ASEAN in Today’s World Program, the three HEIs support ASEAN’s programs in other forms such as through the a) inclusion of subject in the curriculum, i.e REQ-ASEAN integration, b) discussion of ASEAN-related topics in other subjects, c) joining actively in seminars/ trainings in collaboration with AMS, and 4) that an institution of higher learning in the province of Camarines Sur included ASEAN integration in their curriculum and utilized instructional materials for the subject such as a complete set of modules.

Upon gathering the findings along the least implemented action lines, the researcher could conclude that: 1) The three HEIs necessitated some strategies to keep their institutions responsive to the aims of ASED. 2) HEIs have the available teaching resources to use, however, a need to keep them updated and used by the students and teachers are essential. 3) HEIs have existing scholarship programs for their students but none is AMS-sourced since they are less aware of programs being catered by the organization.

Respondent HEIs encountered challenges in the implementation of action lines. Based on the results, the researcher could conclude that: 1) Family financial constraints prevailed as the most challenging since majority of the respondents were

within the middle or average socio-economic status. As a result, students were unable to participate/join in the activities related to ASED; 2) The second most perceived problem was the unavailable resources at home. This was also in relation to the most challenging problem, i.e. family financial constraints. It could be concluded that the respondents were incapable of providing educational resources specific for ASED activities; and 3) That school's support was limited in terms of ASED action lines because these were less prioritized.

Along with these challenges was the discovery that respondents have limited knowledge on ASEAN organization, its ideals and aspirations for education sector in particular. Thus, the present study would be a gateway for a wider array of opportunities to generate information and transfer of knowledge through research undertakings on ASEANOLOGY. This could possibly result to the reduction of gaps between AMS and create a more unified and connected entity dealing with ASEAN-related concerns and its resolutions.

Recommendations

Based on the results and the subsequent analysis, the researcher has formulated the following recommendations:

1) HEIs may conduct benchmarking activities with institutions of higher learning that have successfully implemented student/faculty mobility; credit transfer program. Solicit from them, if possible, some information regarding the procedures and strategies in offering credit transfer program.

2) Continuously conduct ASEAN-related activities such as seminars/ trainings to sustain partnerships with AMS; HEIs may host these events in a face-to-face modality.

3) HEIs may organize ASEAN-related activities to promote ASEAN awareness to the students such as quiz bees, essay writing contests, poster-making competition, song writing competition, and other academic and literary contests, as well as celebration of ASEAN Week.

4) Initiate more activities to promote ASEAN awareness in the school community. These may involve the students, teaching and non-teaching personnel, parents, and other stakeholders of the institution. They may also invite participants from AMS. For instance, the conduct of ASEAN and Education Summit- Institutional/ Regional/ National/ International Level.

5) HEIs may initiate information campaign/ drive for ASEAN awareness, activities, or programs such as documentary analysis, research projects, and singing of regional anthem (ASEAN Way) during the flag ceremony.

6) Utilize more relevant, up-to-date, and accessible educational resources to promote ASEAN awareness.

7) Faculty members from the HEIs in charge of revising their curriculum must attend ASEAN workshops and activities to get updated information that will help them design an ASEAN-aware curriculum.

8) HEIs can plan for annual training-workshop for faculty members handling subjects with ASEAN. This will be a venue to revise or develop a more updated course contents and made them available for utilization in the institution. An electronic or printed copy can be provided to the students and teachers for use. ASEAN information can be access through their official website at <https://asean.org/>.

9) Concerned authorities from HEIs may source out available information or communicate with ASEAN organization. They can visit the organization's website at <https://asean.org/>.

10). ASED-related activities can be conducted by the HEIs in the absence of financial obligations on the part of the students. School administration can seek funding from other government, non-government organizations, or private individuals who support ASEAN-inspired programs.

11) Teaching and learning resources for ASEAN concepts such as educational videos and presentations are archived and accessible at <https://asean.org/>. They can use the available resources online. For instance:

a) ASEAN History - <https://asean.org/the-founding-of-asean/>

b) ASEAN Charter - <https://asean.org/asean-charter/>

c) ASEAN Member States (AMS) - <https://asean.org/member-states/>

d) ASEAN Journey -

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FumQuo6ETBg&t=6s>

e) Towards an ASEAN Higher Education Space: Development, Challenges and Opportunities - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-6JP5ORpaSo>

12) Conduct further study related to the present research specifically on ASEAN awareness. The researchers may choose to examine the educational initiatives undertaken by the ASEAN as the focal point of their investigation. This could encompass an exploration of the organization's efforts in facilitating the transition of students and learners into the workforce through the provision of internship opportunities, scholarships for higher education, and the promotion of responsive skills development. Additionally, the researchers may also explore other notable benefits and action plans that the ASEAN can provide to its community.

13) It was found out that there was an inadequacy in the number of HEI in Camarines Sur with initiatives or action lines appertaining to ASED which could be a contributory factor in advancing knowledge in ASEAN Studies. Thus, it was

necessary to examine the institutions' prospects and policies with a focus on emerging global educational issues. Through research in ASEAN Studies, it would leave a lasting effect on the education sector. Accurate and accessible data would help the HEIs to strengthen ASED action line's implementation and promote conglomerate among HEIs in the country and the AMS through a comprehensive policy making and reform to improve the basic drivers in education, the school, teachers, and students.

14) It was recommended to build institutional capacity in AMS and foster monitoring of the ASED action lines to increase HEIs' and students' access to quality ASEAN Studies programme.

15) The results of this study also shadowed the social and economic conditions of the students which were the determinants of their non-participation to ASED action lines. With this, it was recommended that the transformation of knowledge typically occurred inside the four corners of the room could be distinctively undertaken in a boundlessly-spanning knowledge infrastructure.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENTS & FACULTY/ADMINISTRATOR

Dear Respondents,

The researcher is conducting a study titled: **“THE ASEAN WORK PLAN ON EDUCATION (ASED) IN THE TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAM OF SELECTED HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEIs) IN CAMARINES SUR.”** Your honest self-assessment will be kept with utmost confidentiality. Your full cooperation is highly appreciated.

Thank you very much.

The Researcher

PART 1: Respondents' Demographic Data

Please check the box/fill in the blank with information that applies to you. (**for students*)
(***for faculty/admin*)

*/**NAME OF SCHOOL _____	PRIVATE ☐	PUBLIC ☐
*DEGREE/PROGRAM (*FOR STUDENTS)	BEED ☐	BSE ☐
*MAJOR	MATH ☐	☐
	FILIPINO ☐	☐
	SCIENCE ☐	☐
	ECD ☐	☐
	SPED ☐	☐
OTHERS, PLS SPECIFY	_____	_____
*YEAR LEVEL	4th year ☐	☐
DEGREE/PROGRAM TAUGHT (FOR FACULTY/ADMIN)	BEED ☐	BSE ☐
**COURSE TAUGHT SPECIFY)	**MAJOR (PLS SPECIFY)	_____
	**ELECTIVE (PLS SPECIFY)	_____
**POSITION	President	☐
	Vice-President	☐
	Program Chair	☐
	Dean	☐
	Department Head	☐

	International Relations Officer	☐
	Others pls. specify	_____
**EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	☐
	With units on Master	☐
	Master Degree	☐
	With units in Doctoral	☐
	Doctoral Degree	☐
**NUMBER OF YEARS IN SERVICE	1-5 years	☐
	6-10 years	☐
	11-15 years	☐
	16-20 years	☐
	21-26 years	☐
	27 & above	☐

Part 2. Research Question No. 1: Action Lines in selected HEIs offering Teacher Education Programs

(Noted: Question is indicated in the list of Guide Questions during the interview)

What are the activities/ programs being offered/ conducted by your institution in terms of ASEAN Work Plan in Education from year 2016-2020? Kindly List them down.

Programs/Activities	Date
1.	
2.	
3.	
4.	
5.	
6.	
7.	
8.	
9.	
10.	

Part 3. Research Question No. 2: Action Lines and Extent of its implementation in selected HEIs offering Teacher Education programs

Direction: Please check to which level is it implemented in your school using the scale provided with their interpretation:

Highly Implemented (HI) 4	Moderately Implemented (MI) 3	Slightly Implemented (SI) 2	Not Implemented (NI) 1
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Action Lines for ASED		HI	MI	SI	NI
		4	3	2	1
1.	Develop long-term plan to institutionalize the ASEAN Studies courses as evidenced by a complete set of teaching materials for ASEAN Studies.				
2.	Develop guidelines for cross-border mobility of students and scholars on ASEAN Studies.				
3.	Implement guidelines for cross-border mobility of students and scholars on ASEAN Studies.				
4.	Develop guidelines for cross-border mobility of faculty on ASEAN Studies.				
5.	Implement guidelines for cross-border mobility of faculty on ASEAN Studies.				
6.	Conduct conferences/ seminars/ forums on ASEAN.				
7.	Develop ASEAN regionalism flagship research programs.				
8.	Implement various scholarship programs on ASEAN.				
9.	Support ASEAN in Today's World Program.				
10.	Develop/expand the ASEAN Foundation's initiative to implement Model ASEAN Program.				
11.	Utilizes ASEAN Studies modules and Instructional Manual and made available to university students and educators.				
12.	Update the ASEAN Studies modules and Instructional Manual and made available to university students and educators.				
13.	Conduct survey of existing ASEAN Studies courses.				
14.	Develop guidelines for ASEAN Studies courses (identify structure of ASEAN Studies courses to serve as basis for recognition of an ASEAN Studies courses.				

**Revised Questionnaire from the study conducted by Katigbak and Amante (2019) titled, "ASEAN Integration to Education in Selected Higher Educational Institutions: An Analysis."*

Part 3/ Research Question No. 3: Challenges encountered by the selected HEIs in the implementation of the activities for ASED in TEP.

Direction: Please rank the following challenges encountered by your institution based from its degree of influence in the implementation of ASED action lines. Write No. 1 as the most challenging.

Challenges encountered		Rank
A. SCHOOL-RELATED		
1.	Unsupportive school administrators	
2.	School Financial constraints	
3.	Unsupportive, attitude, beliefs of faculty	
4.	Insufficient/ unavailable school resources/facilities	
5.	School do not recognize ASEAN-related activities or celebrations	
6.	Absence of ASEAN-related courses in the TE Curriculum	
7.	Faculty did not meet the qualifications and skills required for Exchange program	
B. HOME-RELATED		
1.	Unsupportive parents	
2.	Family financial constraints	
3.	Unavailable resources	
C. STUDENT-RELATED		
1.	Students unqualified for Exchange program	
2.	Student's well-being/health condition	
3.	Students' interests towards the activities	

Thank you very much for your time and cooperation.

JENELYN C. AGUELO
Master of ASEAN Studies Student
University of the Philippines Open University

APPENDIX B

GUIDE QUESTIONS FOR INTERVIEW

1. What are the activities/programs being offered/conducted by your institution in terms of ASEAN Work Plan in Education from year 2016-2020? Among these action lines, which are still implemented and sustained until now?
2. What are the ASEAN Member States (AMS) does your institution has linked with from 2016-2020?
3. What are the problems/issues/challenges does your institution had faced in the implementation of the action lines for ASED?
4. How did your university overcome these issues/problems/challenges?

Note: Questions not stated here may still be raised for further clarifications of respondents' responses.

Prepared by:

JENELYN C. AGUELO

MAS Student

APPENDIX C

APPROVED REQUEST LETTER TO CONDUCT THE STUDY

November 23, 2022

ALBERTO N. NAPERI, DPA
SUC President IV
Central Bicol State University of Agriculture

Dear President Naperi:

Warmest greetings!

I am Jenelyn C. Aguelo, a permanent faculty member of Central Bicol State University of Agriculture- Calabanga and pursuing the Master of ASEAN Studies (MAS) program at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU), Los Baños, Laguna. Presently, I am enrolled in the course, ASEAN 300- Thesis Writing.

In line with this, may I respectfully request for your approval to conduct my study titled, "The ASEAN Work Plan in Education (ASED) in Teacher Education Program of the Selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Camarines Sur". The study will generally assess the implementation of action lines in Priority Area 1.3 for ASED of Teacher Education Program of the selected HEIs in the province of Camarines Sur. One of the criteria in the determination of respondent institution is that the HEI must have an existing offering of both the secondary and elementary Teacher Education degree programs. It will involve the purposely selected school administrators and faculty, and randomly selected BSEd and BEEd 4th year students.

In line with this, may I also request the data on the currently enrolled BSEd and BEEd 4th year students from the Registrar's Office so that I can determine the corresponding respondents for my study.

Your affirmative response as regards to this matter will support the ASEAN community to realize the need to deepen the scope of education partnership among the ASEAN Member States (AMS) towards the development of a more coordinate, cohesive and coherent ASEAN position and its contribution to global educational issues.

Attached herewith is the questionnaire to be used in gathering the data for your perusal.

Thank you very much.

Respectfully yours,

JENELYN C. AGUELO, PhD
MAS Student
jenelyn.aguelo@cbsua.edu.ph 0977 1100384

Noted:

E. Dicolan
EMELY D. DICOLEN, PhD
Thesis Adviser

Approved:

[Signature]
ALBERTO N. NAPERI, DPA
SUC President IV
Central Bicol State University of Agriculture

copy of the owner

November 23, 2022

ALEX H. NAVARROZA, PhD
SUC President II
Bicol State College of Applied Sciences and Technology

Dear President Navarroza:

Warmest greetings!

I am Jenelyn C. Aguelo, a permanent faculty member of Central Bicol State University of Agriculture- Calabanga and pursuing the Master of ASEAN Studies (MAS) program at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU), Los Baños, Laguna. Presently, I am enrolled in the course, ASEAN 300- Thesis Writing.

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Thank you very much.

Respectfully yours,

JENELYN C. AGUELO, PhD
MAS Student
jenelyn.aguelo@cbsua.edu.ph / 0977 1100384

Noted:

EMELY D. DICOLEN, PhD
Thesis Adviser

Approved:

ALEX H. NAVARROZA, PhD
SUC President II
Bicol State College of Applied Sciences and Technology

*VPAS + mean
channel
pls observe data
privacy
& ethics in
research*

*received
with
11/28/22
1:20*

Personal copy

November 23, 2022

DR. RAUL G. BRADECINA
University President
Partido State University

Dear President Bradecina:

Warmest greetings!

I am Jenelyn C. Aguelo, a permanent faculty member of Central Bicol State University of Agriculture- Calabanga and pursuing the Master of ASEAN Studies (MAS) program at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU), Los Baños, Laguna. Presently, I am enrolled in the course, ASEAN 300- Thesis Writing.

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Thank you very much.

Respectfully yours,

JENELYN C. AGUELO, PhD
MAS Student
jenelyn.aguelo@cbsua.edu.ph 0977 1100384

Noted:

EMELY D. DICOLEN, PhD
Thesis Adviser

Approved:

DR. RAUL G. BRADECINA
University President
Partido State University

Marifia S. Magat, PhD
Dean, CESE 0951 675 963